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Abstract: In order to achieve hydrophobic properties in textiles, per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are often used. These chemicals represent a class of synthetic compounds that have found wide application in numerous industries because of their advantageous properties, such as hydrophobicity, lipophobicity, chemical inertness, remarkable lubricity, non-stickiness, exceptional fire resistance, resistance to high temperatures, and high resistance to various weathering conditions. However, recent scientific research has demonstrated that these compounds possess persistent, accumulative, and highly mobile properties that make them an environmental hazard. Since the toxicity of PFAS is now recognized, ongoing research has been initiated to explore new substitutes. This comprehensive review focuses on the exploration of natural-based hydrophobic coatings for natural textiles, which include materials such as natural waxes, fatty acids, naturally occurring polymeric compounds (including proteins, carbohydrates, complex aromatic polymers, and polymers like natural rubber), and other naturally occurring substances. The role of each compound in the hydrophobic coating is also highlighted. This review aims to evaluate the potential of natural compounds as viable replacements for PFAS, focusing on their efficiency and durability.

Keywords: hydrophobicity; water contact angle; textile coating; PFAS; nature-based solutions; sustainability

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1. Introduction

The increasing interest in natural textiles is driven by environmental concerns associated with synthetic fibers, particularly their slow biodegradability, and role in contributing to microplastic pollution [1]. Natural textiles, because of the absence of inherent hydrophobic properties, are less used in the field of outerwear and technical textiles [2]. Hydrophobicity is crucial not only for repelling water but also for reducing impurities on textile surfaces, thereby extending the service life of consumer products [3]. There have been several recent studies highlighting concerns over the negative environmental and health impacts of the toxic chemicals traditionally used to enhance these properties. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) have been widely used in this field [4]. Section 2 provides a more detailed discussion on PFAS. Because of their negative impacts and the increasingly strict regulations on their use, current research focuses on developing new PFAS-free alternatives. These alternatives are still predominantly based on synthetic solutions, such as silicones [5], alkylamines [6], and acrylates [7].

Natural products, particularly those derived from plants, are gaining global popularity in the textile industry because of their abundant availability, biocompatibility, renewability, low toxicity, eco-friendly characteristics, and alignment with sustainable, green practices [8]. The same goes for hydrophobic textile coatings, for which natural compounds like polysaccharides [9], proteins [10], natural rubber [11], several natural waxes [12], and other natural compounds, which are described in Section 5, have been researched. Natural-based coatings have a significantly lower environmental footprint. Unlike synthetic solutions, which rely on non-renewable resources, produce significant chemical waste, and often contain persistent compounds that accumulate in ecosystems, natural coatings are biodegradable. They also often adhere better to other natural materials because of their similar chemical compositions. By blending different natural components, it is possible to tailor coatings to specific applications while maintaining their eco-friendly properties. While they can be more affordable than synthetic chemicals because of their availability, their cost varies depending on the type, source, purity, and intended application [8,13]. To overcome the hydrophilic nature of most plant-based materials, chemical modifications and innovative techniques are essential to impart hydrophobic properties [13]. These modification techniques, along with specialized extraction or synthesis processes, are often more expensive than the production of conventional synthetic coatings. Additionally, these coatings can typically only be replicated under strict laboratory conditions [14]. Scaling such technologies for industrial production is also challenging and can incur significant costs [14]. The lack of clear guidelines and industrial standards for natural-based hydrophobic coatings can hold back commercialization and acceptance. In addition, regulatory compliance in different regions further complicates development and scaling efforts [15]. The use of natural compounds for textile coatings can compete with food resources or contribute to deforestation, hence raising ethical and environmental questions. That is why sourcing natural resources from biowaste (including food and agricultural byproducts) is crucial [16]. Coatings derived from natural materials often fail under extreme environmental conditions or during prolonged wear and repeated wash cycles [15,17]. That is why these coatings, most often, still contain amounts of synthetic compounds to achieve adequate hydrophobicity and durability, limiting their biodegradable properties.

The overall sustainability of a natural-based coating depends upon the sourcing practices, energy use during processing, and life-cycle impact of the coatings [17]. A coating is considered eco-friendly if it is applied with as little water and energy as possible and uses only sustainable, green solvents. A perfect green solvent is non-toxic to all living organisms, has low fire and explosion hazards, and degrades in the environment without harmful byproducts. It is important that the coating is durable without drastically changing the characteristics of the textile and, at the same time, to be biodegradable and recyclable to create a closed-loop system. Although the durability of coatings and the biodegradability of materials sound like contradictory properties, many biopolymers balance them; they decompose slowly within a few years and serve their function. This makes them applicable for sustainability purposes [17].

The objective of this review is to explore innovative, PFAS-free hydrophobic solutions partially or entirely derived from natural sources to impart hydrophobic properties to natural textiles. The articles included in this review were required to feature at least one natural compound. This review systematically compiles and analyzes the existing research, providing a curated list of natural compounds used in hydrophobic coatings. It also explores the various roles of compounds in hydrophobic coatings, categorizing the natural compounds previously utilized based on their function in the coating, such as surface roughening agents, low-surface-energy materials, or binders. It compiles the results from reviewed articles on achieved hydrophobicity, using the key parameter of

surface wettability—the water contact angle (WCA), which is defined as the angle formed at the three-phase boundary where liquid, solid, and air meet [18]. The sliding angle (SA), also known as the roll-off angle, was evaluated for superhydrophobic coatings. This angle represents the minimum tilt required for a liquid droplet on the surface to begin sliding or rolling off [19]. We also collected data on other material characterization methods, including durability tests, such as washing (e.g., domestic or laboratory washes of different standards), chemical durability (e.g., immersion of coated textiles in solutions with acidic, alkaline, or neutral pHs), thermal durability (e.g., thermogravimetric analysis), and abrasion resistance (e.g., sandpaper or tape peel tests). Additionally, we gathered results from moisture absorption tests (e.g., gravimetric method and moisture vapor transmission rate) and breathability assessments (air permeability tests). Other properties evaluated include antibacterial activity, UV protection, water–oil separation efficiency (e.g., oil–water separation tests), self-cleaning, and self-healing. This review also offers a brief overview of PFAS coatings and their properties, enabling a comparison with the performance of natural-based alternatives. Through systematic organization and analysis of these data, we assess whether these alternatives can match the efficiency and durability of PFAS coatings. The primary objective is to shed light on current examples of nature-based coatings, aiming to have hydrophobic properties continuously evolving frontier.

2. PFAS—Status Overview of “Forever Chemicals”

PFAS chemicals are a ubiquitous group of organic fluorinated synthetic chemicals that have been widely used in industrial and consumer products since the 1940s. These chemicals are classified as xenobiotics, and their numbers continue to increase as the industry develops new chemicals [20]. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) now states that there are over 9200 unique PFAS structures [21]. The chemical structure of PFAS compounds consists of a carbon chain surrounded by fluorine atoms with different chain lengths and branching. Different PFAS compounds may have different functional groups attached to the chain. One of the characteristic features of PFAS compounds is their strong carbon–fluorine bond. This bond makes PFAS very resistant to degradation by natural processes such as biological decomposition or photolysis [22]. Scientists have been unable to determine their half-life, earning them the nickname “forever chemicals”. This persistence in the environment leads to bioaccumulation in both the environment and living organisms. In addition, PFAS substances are highly mobile due to their diverse chemical and physical properties, allowing them to spread rapidly in the environment. They have been detected in the Arctic, a remote region far from potential sources of contamination [21]. The negative properties of PFAS are illustrated schematically in Figure 1.

PFAS are either in the form of polymers or non-polymers. Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFC) are similar to perfluoroalkyl substances except that not all hydrogen atoms attached to the carbon atoms have been replaced by fluorine atoms [23]. The result is a molecule that is extremely hydrophobic and lipophobic. Their other properties are chemical inertness; they are very slippery, non-sticky, highly fire resistant, can withstand very high temperatures, and are very weather resistant [4]. Because of their unique properties, PFAS are used not only in textiles but in a wide range of applications, including fluoropolymer-coated cookware, water- and oil-resistant food packaging, extreme weather military uniforms, food handling equipment, medical equipment, cosmetics, motor oil additives, fire-fighting foams, paints and inks, and other water-repellent products [4]. The textile industry is a major contributor to the global use of PFAS, accounting for approximately half of its total usage. Based on available data from 2020, the Wood Institute report estimated that 45,000 to 76,000 metric tons of PFAS are used for textile products in the European Union (EU) annually [21]. The most used compound is a group of fluorotelomers (FTOHs), which is

the main subgroup of PFAS. The oil- and water-repellent properties of PFAS make them a popular choice for producing fabrics that can withstand exposure to moisture, dirt, and other environmental factors. They are also commonly employed to treat leather to improve the efficiency of hydrating, pickling, degreasing, and tanning, as well as in the production of household textiles, including carpets and tablecloths [21]. They are also utilized as processing agents to aid in the deposition of dyes and bleaches and to reduce the over-effect in textile treatment baths. Furthermore, they can be used to lubricate yarns, making them easier to weave [24]. The widespread use of PFAS in textiles and outdoor wear poses significant environmental and health risks, as these chemicals are emitted throughout the product life cycle, from production to disposal. During the production phase, textile factories release PFAS into the surrounding environment through air and wastewater emissions, exposing workers and local communities to these harmful chemicals. As textile products are used, PFAS can be released into the environment through weathering, volatilization, and washing, contributing to the pollution of waterways and indoor air [21]. Schellenberger et al. [25] analyzed polyamide (PA) textile fabrics treated with distinct water-repellent, side-chain fluorinated polymers (SFPs). The substrates were subjected to various natural stressors while positioned on a rooftop for 6 months. The results revealed a depletion of PFAS-containing textile fragments, such as microfibers, accompanied by the generation and subsequent depletion of low-molecular-weight PFAS compounds. Research by Robel et al. [26] confirmed that the PFAS concentration is higher in older textiles, suggesting that these materials may pose a greater risk of PFAS exposure than newer ones. When items treated with PFAS are disposed of, PFAS migrates from the waste into the landfill, is emitted with incineration, or is recycled into new products. When those products are recycled, PFAS can spread uncontrollably and contaminate new products and, therefore, those compounds represent a barrier to the circular economy, especially because it is difficult to remove PFAS from fibers once it has been added [20,21]. Humans are continuously exposed to PFAS, especially through drinking water and diet. However, exposure via dust, indoor environments, and personal care and consumer products is also important. A study performed by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), found PFAS in the blood of 97 percent of Americans [27]. Studies have shown that they can penetrate dermally [28] and via inhalation [29] and ingestion [30], ending up in human tissue. They have been found in breast milk, urine, and blood samples [31]. They have been linked to a range of health effects, including cancer [32], reproductive and developmental problems [33], immune system dysfunction [34], endocrine disrupters [35], and thyroid and kidney function disrupters [36]. They are also hepatotoxic [37] and connected to behavioral difficulties [38]. As a result, exposure to PFAS is a growing concern for public health officials and researchers worldwide [20,27]. The life cycle of PFAS and their environmental and health effects are represented in Figure 2.

Current Regulations to Reduce PFAS

To minimize PFAS toxicity, legislation has recently been imposed. Regulations from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the European Union, under the Stockholm Convention, have imposed a mandatory ban on the usage of persistent organic pollutants [39]. This regulation restricts the production and use of perfluorooctanesulfonic and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOS and PFOA) and requires the phaseout of PFOS in textiles and other products. PFOS and PFOA have been replaced with short-chain PFAS, which, despite their lower bioaccumulation potential, are still found ubiquitously in the environment, including remote areas. This preference for short-chain PFAS may be due to the limited research conducted on them rather than concrete evidence of their safety [40]. In June 2022, the Stockholm Convention parties decided to include perfluorohexanesulfonic acid

(PFHxS), its salts, and related compounds in the treaty in 2023. Long-chain perfluorinated carboxylic acids (C9-21 PFCAs) are being considered for inclusion in the Stockholm Convention and consequent global elimination [41]. Numerous PFAS have been included in the Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). Since February 2023, perfluorinated carboxylic acids (C9-14 PFCAs), their salts, and precursors are restricted. The REACH also includes a catalog of substances of very high concern (SVHC). These PFAS compounds have been recognized as posing risks comparable to those of carcinogens, mutagens, and repro toxicants, as well as being categorized as persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic/very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBTs/vPvBs) chemicals [42]. In the United States, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has recently introduced a “significant new use rule” mandating that companies intending to utilize specific long-chain PFAS in novel applications must inform the agency at least 90 days beforehand. This provision enables the EPA to thoroughly assess and decide on the permissibility of the proposed new usage. PFAS was also added to the list of chemicals covered by the Toxics Release Inventory (TRI) Program [21]. However, up to then, there were no regulations for PFAS as a group for textiles [43]. In April 2024, after a three-month transition period, total fluorine (TF) replaced the current limit value for extractable organic fluorine (EOF) for a more effective ban on the intentional use of PFAS. The limit value was adapted to 100 mg/kg for all product classes [44]. In December 2024, The Committees for Risk Assessment (RAC) and for Socio-Economic Analysis (SEAC) reached provisional conclusions on the proposed restriction of PFAS in three sectors, including textiles; upholstery, leather, and apparel; and carpets, so a complete ban of these compounds can be expected in the future in the textile sector [45].

Figure 1. PFAS compounds and their accumulative, persistent, hazardous, and mobile properties.

Figure 2. PFAS life cycle and their environmental and health consequences.

3. Criteria for Hydrophobic Textile Coatings

Hydrophobicity is a solid surface property that allows it to repel water. Surfaces with a WCA greater than 90° are termed hydrophobic. When the WCA exceeds 150° and the water sliding angle is less than 10° , extreme hydrophobicity, called superhydrophobicity, is created. Superhydrophobicity requires a specific surface roughness and low surface energy combination. To develop such surfaces, researchers and industries are increasingly drawing inspiration from nature, mimicking biological systems and structures to create innovative hydrophobic materials [14,15]. Superhydrophobic surfaces are highly sought after because of their potential for numerous advanced applications. These applications range from self-cleaning textiles, oil–water separation, anti-icing or antibacterial coatings, corrosion resistance, smart and functional fabrics, microfluidic devices, water desalination and purification, energy harvesting, optical systems, sensors, and catalytic processes [32]. Fluorine-containing chemicals have been widely used in cotton fabric finishing due to their low surface free energy [46]. We conducted a short overview of a few PFAS hydrophobic textile coatings on natural textiles, as shown in Table 1. The objective of this analysis was to evaluate the hydrophobicity, durability, changes in mechanical properties, breathability, and other key characteristics of PFAS coatings. The results set a benchmark for aspiring nature-based solutions that must be met or exceeded by performance metrics to serve as PFAS substitutes.

Table 1. A summary of PFAS-based hydrophobic coatings and their properties, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
cotton	PHFBA, SiO ₂ nanoparticles, initiated chemical vapor deposition (iCVD) method	WCA = 155°, 5 different sites per sample	N/A	WD (3 washing cycles, soaking in cherry juice for 1 h, laundered for 5 min with a detergent, followed by rinsing and drying)—WCA = 155°, thermolysis: no obvious change in thermolysis temperature after modification	[47]
cotton	PFA), grafting via dip-pad-cure (DPC) process, electron beam irradiation (EBI)	WCA (DPC) = 140°, WCA (EB) = 137°, 3 samples/set	MP bending rigidity (DPC, warp) = −45%, (EB, warp) = −54%, bending hysteresis (DPC, warp) = −40%, (EB, warp) = −36%	WD (10 washing cycles)—WCA = 130°	[46]
cotton	fluoroalkyl acrylate modified polysiloxane, dip-pad	WCA = 145 (±2)°, 5 different sites per sample	MP bending rigidity (0.5 PFAS concentration, warp) = −22%, weft = −11%	TD decomposition at 570 °C	[5]
flax	fluorinated (meth)acrylic monomers, radio grafting using a pre-irradiation procedure	WCA (10% fluorine content, 20, 50, 100 kG) = 150 (±3)°, DCA (10% fluorine content, 332.2 g/mol mass, 5kGY dose) = 120°, 5 different sites per sample	self-cleaning	N/A	[48]
cotton	APDMS, polyurethane (PU), polyfluoroalkoxy (PFA), SiO ₂ nanoparticles, etching, dip coating	WCA = 155 (±1)°, SA = 8°, 5 different sites per sample	strength = 3 MPa, velocity = 0.5 m/s	WD (240,000 cycles: thickness)—WCA = 142°, CD (acid, neutral, alkali)s—WCA = 155°, AR (250,000 cycles)—WCA = 143 (±2)°	[49]

Şimşek et al. [47] deposited poly(hexafluorobutyl acrylate) (PHFBA) and SiO₂ nanoparticles via the initiated chemical vapor deposition (iCVD) method and achieved a WCA of 155° on a cotton substrate with good washing resistance. No effects of thermolysis were observed when samples were heat treated.

Jiang et al. [46] conducted a study in which cotton was modified using the following two distinct methods: the traditional dip-pad-cure (DPC) technique with perfluorooctyl acrylate (PFA)- irradiation through electron beam (EB) exposure. Both approaches yielded comparable WCA results, with DPC resulting in a WCA of 140° and EB achieving 137°. After undergoing 10 wash cycles, the samples exhibited good durability. The treated cotton fabrics exhibited reduced bending rigidity and bending hysteresis compared to the control samples.

Jin et al. [5] employed an extended chain fluoroalkyl acrylate to modify the polysiloxane to enhance the hydrophobic characteristics of the finalized fabric while preserving its inherent softness. The experimental procedure was carried out on cotton fabric using the dip-pad technique, resulting in WCA reaching 145 (±2)°. The authors attribute these high WCA values to the synergistic influence of the following two factors: the inherently low surface free energy of the perfluorinated side chains and the relatively elevated surface roughness of the cotton fibers.

Taibi et al. [48] conducted a study in which they employed a pre-irradiation procedure to graft fluorinated monomers onto flax fibers. The research encompassed a diverse array of monomer types and concentrations. An additional variable involved exposing the fibers to varying doses of e-beam radiation. The highest contact angle of $150 (\pm 3)^\circ$ was achieved for samples irradiated at 20, 50, and 100 kGy and treated with 10 wt% fluorinated monomer with the longest chain. The researchers inferred that the hydrophobic and oleophobic traits of the treated fabrics were contingent upon both the concentration of fluorine and the length of the fluorinated chain. Fabrics treated with a fluorine monomer possessing a molar mass of 532 g/mol displayed SA values below 10° , suggesting the potential presence of self-cleaning characteristics on the treated surfaces.

Wang et al. [49] successfully developed an advanced superhydrophobic coating through the synergistic combination of cotton fiber fabric hydrophobization and the curing process of epoxy composites enriched with polyurethane (PU), polyfluoroalkoxy (PFA), and hydrophobic SiO₂ nanoparticles. The resulting coating unveiled superhydrophobic properties, boasting a WCA of $155 (\pm 1)^\circ$. In-depth tribological assessments unveiled the coating's exceptional performance in the face of rigorous conditions, including a stress of 3 MPa and a sliding velocity of 0.5 m/s. These evaluations confirmed the coating's capacity to maintain stable friction coefficients and exhibit good abrasion resistance withstanding 24,000 abrasion cycles. Moreover, the coating demonstrated commendable durability in both acidic and alkaline solutions, highlighting its versatile protective attributes.

4. The Role of Compounds in Hydrophobic Coatings

Figure 3 emphasizes natural compounds used in hydrophobic coatings, categorized by their specific role in the hydrophobization process.

Hydrophobic coatings usually contain surface roughening materials, low-surface-energy materials, and binders. A general strategy for creating superhydrophobic textiles is to first create surface roughness to enhance the hydrophobicity, followed by applying low-surface-energy materials to maximize water repellency [15].

4.1. Low-Surface-Energy Materials

The wettability is directly connected to the surface energy of the contact surface [15]. High surface energy means a strong molecular attraction, while low surface energy means weaker attractive forces. Water penetrates materials with a high surface energy but forms droplets on materials with low surface energy, as presented in Figure 4. Since natural textiles typically have high surface energy, they must be treated with low-surface-energy compounds to achieve hydrophobicity [17]. If the surface energy of a solid is higher than that of a liquid, the liquid spreads on the surface of the solid to reduce the contact area between the solid and air, which reduces the surface energy. On the other hand, if the surface energy of a solid is less than that of a liquid, the liquid does not spread but instead forms spherical droplets. Thus, solids with lower surface energy are more hydrophobic. Guided by this principle, most of the research on superhydrophobic materials focuses on how to decrease the surface energy of the material [15]. Examples of low-surface-energy materials in nature are waxes, fatty acids, some proteins, betulin, etc. In Figure 3, compounds that can lower the surface energy of natural textiles to some degree and have been used in research for this purpose are listed.

Figure 3. The role of natural compounds in hydrophobic coatings.

Figure 4. The behavior of a water droplet on high-surface- and low-surface-energy materials.

4.2. Surface Roughening Materials

It has been very well documented that surface roughness enhances the hydrophobicity of any hydrophobic solid. While the static contact angle of water usually ranges between 100° and 120° on flat hydrophobic surfaces, surface roughness or micro-texturing can increase the contact angles significantly, often up to very high values between 150° and 175° , as presented in Figure 5 [50]. Most leaves with impressive hydrophobicity have a hierarchical surface roughness, with micro- and nanostructures of unwettable wax crystals. This further enhances the hydrophobicity, making water droplets near-spherical on such a surface. Such leaves generally possess self-cleaning properties; water droplets roll off easily, carrying dirt and debris with them [50].

Figure 5. The importance of surface roughness for superhydrophobicity.

Surface roughness can be achieved with nanoparticles deposition, chemical etching of the surface (for example, enzymatic etching), and physical etching that can, for example, be achieved by plasma treatment or laser ablation [51]. Polysaccharides, proteins, and some other natural compounds that usually exhibit hydrophilic properties are often used in the form of nanoparticles. In Figure 3, compounds that can roughen the surface of natural textiles and have been used in research for this purpose are listed.

4.3. Binders

The binder (schematically presented in Figure 6) is highly important for the dispersion and entrapment of hydrophobic agents and simultaneously provides a strong base layer for the coating [52]. The properties of the binder determine key characteristics of the entire coating regarding mechanical properties like flexibility, strength, and adhesion. Binders are usually polymeric and of high molecular weight; thus, they largely determine the structure and behavior of the coating. The nature and specific properties of the polymer binder will also determine the nature of the coating, its application method, and the conditions that have to be provided for film formation. In addition to providing durability and

flexibility, binders can offer further benefits like enhanced adhesion, improved breathability, or increased UV resistance [52]. Natural binders are often different natural polymers like polysaccharides, protein, and natural rubber. Some of these compounds also have the possibility of crosslinking. Natural binders are listed in Figure 3.

Figure 6. Schematic of a binder.

5. Overview of Natural-Resource-Based Hydrophobic Coatings for Textiles

Even though all PFAS alternatives are described as more environmentally friendly compared to PFAS compounds, synthetic alternatives usually involve environmentally unfriendly and/or toxic components. Despite our desire to overview only natural-based solutions, it is not possible because most of the research combines natural-based alternatives with synthetic PFAS-free compounds. For this reason, we looked into solutions that include natural compounds. Those compounds are presented in Figure 7. The exact characteristics of all mentioned research can be found in the tables within each section.

5.1. Lipids

Lipids are generally characterized by a high molecular weight and distinctive structural features [13]. They represent a diverse group of amphipathic molecules consisting of a hydrophilic (water-attracting) head group and one or more hydrophobic (water-repelling) hydrocarbon chains. They are insoluble in water but readily soluble in nonpolar organic solvents [13]. In contact with water, lipids display a remarkable diversity of self-organizing behaviors, as follows: the formation of monolayers at air–water interfaces; assembly into micelles, bilayers, or vesicles; and basic building blocks of biological membranes [53]. These properties are the result of the intense cohesive forces of water molecules that push the hydrophobic segments of lipids to minimize their contact with the aqueous environment [13,54]. One of the most well-known examples of natural hydrophobicity based on lipids is that of lotus leaves. These leaves are superhydrophobic due to a combination of natural hydrophobic waxes and a nano-scale rough surface structure [54].

Figure 7. Natural compounds used in hydrophobic coatings for natural textiles.

5.1.1. Natural Waxes

Wax refers to a substance that is a plastic solid at ambient temperature and becomes viscous liquid at elevated temperatures. The intricate chemical content of waxes involves a wide array of components, frequently encompassing extended hydrophobic molecules like fatty acids, hydrocarbons, alcohols, ketones, aldehydes, and esters [55]. Among the options presented by nature, waxes stand out as some of the most hydrophobic surfaces [56]. They can be either renewable or non-renewable. Renewable waxes are obtained either from plants or insects, and non-renewable are obtained from minerals [56]. Examples of plant waxes are carnauba wax, candelilla, jojoba, sunflower, and rice bran wax. Known examples of animal waxes are beeswax, shellac wax, wool wax, and spermaceti wax [57]. Natural renewable waxes are also available and economically feasible, which is why researchers

have become interested in their use, especially as advanced superhydrophobic surfaces in numerous applications [56]. Waxes also have bioactive properties. Extracts from several citrus peels have been reported to be antibacterial and antifungal. Eucalyptus globulus leaf waxes have been reported to have antioxidant activity [57]. Coatings made only from waxes often suffer from durability issues, such as poor mechanical and tribological properties, poor thermal stability, and fast leaching. For this reason, they are often used in combination with organic polymers or nanoparticles [56]. An example of wax deposition on natural textile is presented in Figure 8. In Table 2, a summary of studies using natural wax is presented.

Figure 8. Deposition of natural wax via layer-by-layer (LBL) self-assembly technique, according to Forsman et al. [12].

Forsman et al. [12] developed an open bio-based coating from a dispersion of natural carnauba wax, poly-L-lysine (PLL), and a dispersion of natural carnauba wax and cationic starch (CS) on cellulosic textiles as a cheaper alternative to PLL. The application of the coating can be accomplished through methods such as immersion, spraying, or brushing. The highest WCA of 155° was achieved with two bilayers of PLL at 70°C . The authors elucidate this phenomenon through variations in melting temperatures among distinct compounds within carnauba wax. Additionally, they highlight the molecular rearrangement occurring in the outermost wax layer, where more hydrophobic molecules or components tend to accumulate at the wax/air interface. This restructuring aims to reduce the surface energy. A bilayer composed of CS and wax exhibited a marginally reduced WCA compared to a bilayer of PLL/wax. This variation can be attributed to the inherent hydrophobic characteristics of PLL. The deposition of two bilayers was optimal to achieve adequate hydrophobicity. More layers achieved an even higher hydrophobicity but lowered its permeability. One layer provided a hydrophobicity of 95° , and after two bilayers it increased to 140° . The two bilayers of CS/wax had approximately the same WCA as one bilayer of PLL/wax. The coating did not affect the breathability of the textiles because of the thin layer and the fact that it was applied only on textile fibers and did not cover the holes in the textile surface. The authors observed that the surface roughness of the initial material influences the final hydrophobicity of the coated material. Nonetheless, the primary factor contributing to the roughness is the submicron texture introduced by the wax particles.

Bashari et al. [58] created a novel hydrophobic and antibacterial coating by employing a layer-by-layer (LBL) self-assembly technique. This method involved utilizing carnauba wax with a negative charge and CS with a positive charge. The optimal coating comprised five layers. The hydrophobic properties of cotton textiles were enhanced, as evident by a WCA of 131° . However, after subjecting the coated textiles to washing, the WCA decreased to 102° . The introduced coating did not have a discernible impact on the air permeability of the textiles, and the fabric's tactile qualities remained unaffected.

In another study, Bashari et al. [59] achieved water-repellent and antibacterial properties of cotton with carnauba wax nanoparticles (CWNs) and zinc oxide (ZnO) via the LBL self-assembly method. The plasma treatment was used to functionalize the fabric's surface. The WCA of such treated cotton was 131° . A drop of water stayed on the surface of the fabric for more than three minutes without spreading. After the washing procedure, the WCA decreased to 103° .

Another option is to use plants that are covered with a layer of bio-wax that is highly hydrophobic and to use them in the form of extracts. Plant epicuticular wax refers to the organic components of the cuticle that covers the outer surface of aerial plant tissues [3].

Singh et al. [3] developed a hydrophobic coating for cotton fabric using taro-root leaf extract in combination with TiO_2 nanoparticles and beeswax. Cotton-fabric coated with leaf extract, beeswax, and TiO_2 nanoparticles achieved a contact angle of 128° . The addition of TiO_2 nanoparticles enhances the surface roughness. Beeswax is naturally soft and flexible, so it adds some pliability to the cotton cloth by closing the pores of the fabric. Without beeswax, the coating achieved a WCA of 104° . The WCA of cotton treated only with leaf extract yielded a CA of 96° .

Zhang et al. [60] used beeswax in combination with lignin, as further described in Section 5.2.2 Lignin.

Table 2. A summary of studies that fabricated hydrophobic textile coatings using natural wax, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% weave cotton, 100% knit cotton, blend (55% hemp, 45% natural carnauba wax)	natural carnauba wax, poly-L-lysine (PLL)/cationic starch, LBL, dipping/spraying/brushing	WCA (cotton, carnauba wax + PLL) = $155 (\pm 15)^\circ$, SA (cotton, carnauba wax + PLL) = 9° , 3 samples/set	WVTP (cotton, carnauba wax + PLL) = -0.4%	N/A	[12]
100% cotton	carnauba wax, chitosan, LBL, dipping	WCA = 131° , 2 samples/set	MP bending length = $+6\%$, WVTP = -34% , AP = -34% , ANT P. (<i>S. aureus</i>) = 96% , (<i>E. coli</i>) = 95%	WD (ISO 105-C06 Test Method [61])—WCA = 102°	[58]
100% cotton	carnauba wax nanoparticles, ZnO nanoparticles, plasma pre-treatment with O_2 , layer-by-layer dip-coating	WCA = 131° , 3 samples/set, 2 different sites	antibacterial effect (<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i>) = 100%	WD (N/A)—WCA = 103°	[59]
100% cotton	taro-root leaves extract, TiO_2 nanoparticles, beeswax, dip coating	WCA (taro root, TiO_2 beeswax) = $128 (\pm 2)^\circ$, WCA (taro root) = $96 (\pm 9)^\circ$, WCA (taro root, TiO_2) = $104 (\pm 2)^\circ$, WCA (taro root, beeswax) = $112 (\pm 6)^\circ$	N/A	N/A	[3]

5.1.2. Fatty Acids

Fatty acids (FAs, schematic provided in Figure 9) are essential organic compounds that play important roles in numerous biological processes within living organisms. They exhibit variations in the length of their carbon chains and can exist in either a saturated

form or contain one or more double bonds separated by at least one methylene group. Saturated fatty acids (SFAs) are straight hydrocarbon chains with an even number of carbon atoms. They are filled (i.e., saturated) with hydrogen. Most often they contain 12–22 carbon atoms. They are filled (i.e., saturated) with hydrogen. Most often they contain 12–22 carbon atoms. Monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) have one carbon–carbon double bond that can occur in different positions. Most common MUFAs have a chain length of 16–22 and a double bond with *cis* configuration, causing the carbon tails to bend or form kinks in unsaturated FAs [62]. Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) have the first double bond between the third and fourth carbon atoms from the *n*-carbon and are called *n*-3, or omega-3 fatty acids. Additionally, there is a distinct group of FAs, referred to as branched-chain FAs, characterized by acyl branches connected to the hydrocarbon chain [63]. The properties of FAs depend significantly on their structure, particularly the degree of desaturation and chain length. Unsaturated FAs generally exhibit a lower melting point compared to saturated FAs. This difference arises because the hydrocarbon chain of saturated FAs tends to favor highly ordered molecule packing, leading to an increase in the melting point of FAs. In contrast, the presence of double bonds in unsaturated FAs disrupts this packing, resulting in a lower melting point. The water solubility of FAs is influenced by their hydrocarbon chain length as well. FAs generally have low solubility in water due to their increased hydrophobicity with longer chain lengths. Additionally, their solubility is hindered by their ability to form micelles and monolayers in aquatic environments. However, the water solubility of FAs can be enhanced when they are in the form of potassium or sodium salts or when the medium has a higher pH. On the contrary, FAs easily dissolve in nonpolar solvents like ethanol and chloroform. The chemical stability of fatty acids depends on the number of double bonds in the molecule. More double bonds mean higher reactivity. For hydrophobic coatings, stearic acid (STA) is mostly used. A summary of studies using fatty acids is presented in Table 3.

Figure 9. Molecular structure of stearic acid.

Cabrales et al. [64] used oleic acid as a hydrophobic agent, which is derived from various plant seed oils, to functionalize 100% cotton fabric using microwave plasma technology. Non-polymerizing gas argon was used to create plasma. This generated radicals on cellulose surface, which were used to initiate copolymerization reactions with oleic acid. Grafted cotton samples showed excellent water repellency with a WCA higher than 150°. The coating showed good durability and retained superhydrophobicity even after 10 days of immersion in oil and water.

Metal oxide nanoparticles are commonly combined with fatty acids for various applications. For instance, in a study by Cheng et al. [65], hydrophobized cotton was developed for efficient oil/water separation. This was achieved using a spray-coating technique that

employed sebacic-acid-cured epoxidized soybean oil (CESO) as the adhesive, nano-ZnO particles to create a rough surface structure, and stearic acid to modify the surface's energy properties. The water contact angle reached 155° . The superhydrophobic fabric exhibited outstanding performance in effectively separating water mixtures from different oily liquids, with a separation efficiency of over 97.5%. Figure 10 presents the oil–water separation efficiencies of the studies referenced in this review (where such data are available), alongside a comparison with the WCA. It is evident that a higher WCA enables a greater oil–water separation efficiency.

Figure 10. Oil–water separation efficiency in relation to WCA.

Arfaoui et al. [66] developed a hydrophobic treatment for jute fibers by grafting and growing ZnO nanorods on their surface. ZnO nanorod fibers were immersed in a solution containing hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA) and zinc nitrate hexahydrate (ZnNi). This solution was then carefully coated onto the jute substrate. To ensure uniform growth of ZnO nanorods on the fiber surface, a hydrothermal process was employed. Following this, an immersion in a solution of STA was carried out. The deposition of ZnO nanorods increased the initial WCA; however, it did not surpass 90° . Through an additional STA treatment, the WCA substantially escalated to 148° . This hydrophobization process had no adverse effects on the thermal stability of the fibers, and there was a limited reduction in strength.

In a separate study [67], the same lead author used a combination of TiO_2 nanoparticles and STA. The TiO_2 nanoparticles were synthesized via sol-gel using three different concentrations of ethanol. After immersion in TiO_2 solution the samples were impregnated with STA. After subjecting the nonwoven substrates to the TiO_2 nanoparticle pre-treatment, a transition to superhydrophilicity occurred. This notable change can be ascribed to the elevated polarity of the Ti–O–Ti groups present. After additional treatment with STA, the substrate became hydrophobic with a WCA of $132 (\pm 4)^\circ$ (for a lower ethanol concentration) to $135 (\pm 3)^\circ$ (for a higher ethanol concentration). Significantly, the application of this hydrophobic treatment did not adversely impact the mechanical performance or thermal stability of the nonwoven substrates.

Xu et al. [68] introduced a method to etch the surface of cotton fibers, utilizing a moderately deep eutectic solvent (DES) instead of traditional inorganic/organic particles that often cause limited durability and degradation of the mechanical properties caused by etching. Initially, the cotton underwent etching by immersing it in a DES solution. The

treated fabric was coated with a thermoset derived from epoxidized soybean oil (ESO) and further enhanced by the introduction of STA, followed by a heat treatment process. As a result of these modifications, the cotton fabric exhibited superhydrophobic properties, boasting a WCA of 160° . The analyses show that the coating does not drastically change the inherent properties of cotton. The resulting fabric's flexibility, mechanical strength, and elongation at the break were reduced, but the reduction degree was still within an acceptable range. The water vapor transmission permeability (WVTP) and water absorption of three finished fabrics have not changed. The durability test showed good results. After undergoing 1000 abrasion cycles, the WCA of the samples remained high at 158° . Moreover, the fabric exhibited resistance to various chemical substances. The finished fabric also shows outstanding self-cleaning properties against solid dust and shows the potential to inhibit protein attachment. The coating also exhibited good oil-separation properties.

In a separate study [69], the same lead author employed fatty acids as low-surface-energy compounds and phytic acid to etch cotton fabric. This etching process effectively enhanced the fabric's surface roughness. Subsequently, the treated fabric underwent a coating process with thermosets derived from epoxidized soybean oil (ESO) and was then layered with STA. The final cotton fabric displayed a WCA of 156° . Certain inherent properties of cotton, such as flexibility, experienced only slight decreases. While the modifications had a minor impact on the fabric's WVTP and water absorption capacity, they remained within an acceptable range. The samples exhibited good abrasion and chemical and thermal stabilities.

Liu and colleagues [70] explored hydrophobic modification of flax fibers through acylation facilitated by lipase activity, conducted in the presence of canola oil. This process resulted in the surface roughening of the fibers, leading to a significant reduction in water uptake, which decreased by 2% after 500 min compared to untreated fibers with a water uptake of 6%. This reduction can be attributed to the presence of hydrophobic fatty acid chains following acylation, as well as the enhanced efficiency of the enzyme-catalyzed acylation reaction. Furthermore, a major contributing factor is the esterification of most hydroxyl groups within the lignocellulosic fibers. This modification resulted in noticeable improvements in both tensile strength and strain at break.

Zhong et al. [71] conducted a study in which they grafted aliphatic fatty acid chains of varying lengths onto the surface of cotton fibers. This modification resulted in cotton with hydrophobic properties, as evidenced by WCAs of $136 (\pm 1)^\circ$, $135 (\pm 2)^\circ$, $136^\circ (\pm 3)$, and $139 (\pm 4)^\circ$ for synthetic heptanoic acid and natural octanoic acid, dodecanoic acid, and stearic acid, respectively. The research findings highlighted the significant influences of heating time and power on the level of hydrophobicity achieved. It was expected that different chain lengths of fatty acids would also affect the water contact angle, given that longer alkyl chains typically possess lower surface energy, thus leading to increased hydrophobicity. However, the study's results revealed only a minimal 3° difference between heptanoic acid with 7 carbon atoms and stearic acid containing 18 carbon atoms. This discrepancy is likely attributed to the limited number of grafted fatty acyl groups on the cotton's surface. The authors suggest the optimization of the grafting process to achieve a higher grafting level, potentially resulting in significantly higher WCAs and rendering the cotton fabric superhydrophobic. Regarding the tensile stress at break, it initially exhibited a gradual decrease with higher power and longer treatment times, likely due to the elevated temperature generated during microwave treatment, which can lead to cellulose degradation. These conditions contributed to higher WCAs. The hydrophobicity was proven to be enduring after the washing durability test.

Dankovich et al. [72] improved the WCA of cotton with triglycerides from several plant oils including soybean, rapeseed, olive, and coconut oils, all containing fatty acids.

However, this process did not achieve a hydrophobic water contact angle. Based on the previously mentioned research, it is evident that fatty acids alone are insufficient in achieving a hydrophobic contact angle. To achieve this, they must be combined with a process that creates surface roughness.

Table 3. A summary of studies that fabricated hydrophobic textile coatings using fatty acids, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	oleic acid, argon (plasma), plasma treatment, immersion	WCA > 150° 3 samples per set	N/A	N/A	[64]
100% cotton	CESO, ZnO, STA, spray coating	WCA = 155°	N/A	N/A	[65]
100% jute fabric	ZnO nanoparticles, STA, ethanol, scouring pre-treatment, grafting, dip coating	WCA (ZnO, STA) = 148 (±9)°, WCA (ZnO) = 55 (±10)°, WCA (STA) = 110 (±10)°, 5 samples per set	MP breaking force (ZnO) = −9%, breaking force (ZnO, STA) = −32%	TD (ZnO, seeding step) = −8%, (ZnO nanorod grafting step) = +4%, (STA) = 0%	[66]
100% jute fabric	TiO ₂ , STA, sol-gel	WCA (TiO ₂ + STA) = 135 (±3)°, WCA (STA) = 127 (±5)°, 5 samples per set	MP ultimate tensile strength = +20%, (specific breaking load) = +7%	TD (TiO ₂ + STA) = +10% (316 °C)	[67]
100% cotton	DES, CESO, STA, etching, dip-coating	WCA = 160 (±0.5)°, 5 samples per set	MP elongation = −23%, tensile breaking strength = −22%, WVTP—not changed, water absorption ability = −11%	WD (30 washing cycles)—WCA = 154 (±2)°, AR (1000 cycles)—WCA > 158 (±1)°, TD (5 h, 100 °C)—WCA > 158 (±0.5)° CD (ethanol, THF, N-hexane, and DMF acetone, 72 h)—WCA > 150 (±3)°	[68]
100% cotton	PA, ESO, STA, etching, dip coating, crosslinking	WCA = 156 (±1)°, 5 samples per set	WVTP (PA, ESO, STA) = −1%, water absorption ability (PA, ESO, STA) = −4%	WD (30 washing cycles)—WCA = 154 (±1)°, AR (after 1200 washing cycles)—WCA = 155 (±3)°, CD (HCl, NaOH, acetone, 6 h)—WCA > 150° TS (6 h, 100 °C)—WCA > 154 (±0.5)°;	[69]
100% flax	lipase, canola oil, acylation	water uptake = 1.7% in 500 min, 3 samples per set	MP tensile strength = −22%, strain at break = +0.8%, Young’ modulus = +42%	N/A	[70]
100% cotton	fatty anhydride, heptanoic/octanoic/dodecanoic/stearic acid, chemical grafting by plasma	WCA for 100% power/15 min (heptanoic acid) = 136 (±1)°, WCA (octanoic acid) = 135 (±2)°, WCA (dodecanoic acid) = 136 (±3)°, WCA (stearic acid) = 139 (±4)°, 3 different sites per sample	MP tensile stress at break (100% power/15 min, warp) = −47%, (100% power/15 min, weft) = −51%	WD (AATCC 61-2023 [73], 37 laboratory wash cycles)—WCA = 108°	[71]

5.2. Natural Polymers

Natural polymers are materials that widely occur in nature or are extracted from plants or animals and are composed of repeating structural units [74]. They are also known as macromolecules or biopolymers and play essential roles in various biological

processes. Recently, the use of natural polymers has been of great interest because of their renewable properties and abundance [75]. Next to this they are biodegradable, biocompatible, non-toxic, more economical, and easily available [76]. However, when working with these polymers, the risk of microbial contamination significantly escalates. The manufacturing of natural polymers is inherently dependent on environmental variables and a range of physical factors. Consequently, it lacks the precision of a controlled process, resulting in noticeable disparities among different batches of samples. These disparities can emerge from temporal variations, geographical distinctions, species diversity, and climatic impacts, all contributing to fluctuations in the chemical composition of a given material. Additionally, natural polymers typically exhibit a slower production rate when compared to their synthetic counterparts [76]. Natural polymers have great potential as natural colloidal materials, such as whey protein, soy glycinin, kafirin, zein, starch, chitosan, polylactic acid, casein, and cellulose. They could satisfy the present demand for eco-friendly stabilizers due to their renewability, nontoxicity, and amphipathicity [77].

5.2.1. Carbohydrates

In the realm of carbohydrates, polysaccharides stand out as valuable components for the formulation of hydrophobic coatings. They are abundantly present in nature, readily sourced from a variety of organisms including algae (e.g., alginates), plants (e.g., pectin, guar gum, and mannan), microbes (e.g., dextran and xanthan gums), and animals (e.g., chitosan and chondroitin). Furthermore, modern biotechnology has enabled the production of polysaccharides through advanced methods such as recombinant deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) techniques [75]. Despite the hydrophilic nature of most polysaccharides, they can also be used in hydrophobic coatings as they work as binders in hydrophobic coatings. They create a protective layer on the textile surface and bind to the hydrophobic molecules in the coating [52]. In the form of nanoparticles, they are also often used to improve the surface roughness [13]. Additionally, they can improve the durability and flexibility of the coating. They can provide additional benefits such as improved adhesion, increased breathability, and enhanced ultraviolet (UV) resistance [52]. A summary of studies using polysaccharides can be found in Table 4. Figure 11 presents a schematic of polysaccharide deposition on natural textiles.

Figure 11. Deposition of CNCs and chitosan via the pad-dry-curing method, as described by Yang et al. [78].

Cellulose

The prevailing natural polymer in widespread use is cellulose. Cellulose stands as an organic polysaccharide, represented by the formula $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$. It comprises a linear arrangement of numerous $\beta(1 \rightarrow 4)$ linked D-glucose units, ranging from a few hundred to

well over ten thousand in number. Its macroscopic morphology is always in the shape of fibers [79]. This compound takes center stage as the primary constituent of plant cell walls. Cellulose is insoluble in water and indigestible by the human body [76]. There are three distinct types of cellulose. Cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs), characterized by diameters ranging from 10 to 100 nm and a high aspect ratio, are obtained through extensive mechanical treatment, involving the separation of cellulose fiber microfibrils. Another variant, known as cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs), takes shape by hydrolyzing the amorphous regions within cellulose fiber bundles, resulting in short rod-shaped crystalline nanoparticles. CNCs possess a significant surface area, excellent chemical reactivity, and favorable rheological properties, endowing nanocellulose with unique capabilities in paper coatings. Bacterial cellulose (BC), on the other hand, is a natural nanocellulose secreted by specific bacteria. It boasts exceptional physical and mechanical properties, as well as high purity. BC predominantly finds applications in the fields of biomedicine and nanocomposites. Additionally, cellulose can be chemically modified to yield carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) through etherification and hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC) through esterification. These modified forms of cellulose serve various purposes and have diverse applications [52]. While the exploration of naturally derived compounds for CNC modification holds promise, contemporary research predominantly revolves around the synergy of synthetic compounds in this context.

Cheng et al. [80] introduced an innovative method by incorporation of CNCs to create a textured surface. This process involved dip-coating, with CESO acting as the binding agent. Upon the application of CNCs atop the CESO layer, the cotton's woven structure remained unchanged, but the cellulosic fibers' surface transformed, resulting in a textured appearance. Additionally, hexadecyltrimethoxysilane (HDTS) was introduced as a low-surface-energy modifier. The FTIR spectra confirmed the successful formation of ester bonds by CESO and the successful grafting of HDTS, indicated by the appearance of a new peak in the Si-O range. The CESO significantly increased the contact angle, raising it to 115°. Following the addition of CNC, the WCA increased to 143°. Subsequent application of HDTS further elevated the WCA to 157°, making the material highly suitable for water/oil separation applications. The resulting superhydrophobic cotton fabric demonstrated good chemical durability. Over time, the contact angle gradually reduced to 138°, reflecting the gradual destruction of the superhydrophobic material's surface structure. This underscores the importance of considering the long-term sustainability and practical viability of this innovative approach.

Yang et al. [78] developed a nanocomposite coating comprising chitosan and CNCs. This coating acted as a modifier and was applied to cotton fabric using a pad-dry-cure method. Hydrophobicity, increased with higher concentrations of CNCs. The 1 wt% CNC/CS coating resulted in a WCA of 135°. Even after 120 s, the WCA remained at around 130° for this concentration, while lower CNC concentrations (0.5 wt%) or without CNC exhibited a decline in WCA after 10 s. The enhanced hydrophobicity of the CS/cotton fabric was attributed to the inherent hydrophilicity of CS, while CNCs influenced by their crystalline and oriented molecular structure, contributed to reduced fabric hydrophilicity. Furthermore, CS and CNCs formed a network structure, limiting the flexibility of the chitosan molecular chain and further decreasing its hydrophilicity. All of the modified fabrics exhibited improved break strength and elongation at break compared to the untreated cotton fabric, with better results observed at lower CNC concentrations. This was attributed to the better dispersion of CNCs in the chitosan solution. However, it was observed that at a relatively high CNC content, agglomeration occurred in the nanocomposite solution, leading to defect points on the fabric's surface. Under external forces, the stress concentration at these points resulted in decreased mechanical properties. The coating offered the added

advantage of enhancing UV protection, showing that CNCs are an effective component to block UV rays. Laundering tests demonstrated the durability of the coating.

Roy et al. [81] devised an innovative method to create a sustainable superhydrophobic coating aimed at producing fabrics with self-cleaning and self-healing properties. The coating formulation utilized cellulose nanofibers (CNFs), derived from hardwood pulp through a TEMPO oxidation process. In their approach, a coating solution comprising CNFs, ethanol, and octadecylamine (ODA) was expertly applied to the fabric using a spray-coating technique. The CNFs introduced surface roughness to the substrate, while the grafting of ODA's hydrocarbon chains effectively lowered the surface energy. This treatment led to an increase in the WCA, achieving a value of $152 (\pm 3)^\circ$. Comparative analysis between untreated and treated cotton fabric revealed notable improvements, with a 3% increase in tensile strength and a 14% enhancement in the Young's modulus for the coated fabric. These results underscored the strong adhesion between the fibers and the cellulose coating, rendering the fibers mechanically robust and less flexible than their uncoated counterparts. Additionally, the coating exhibited impressive self-cleaning capabilities when exposed to various powders and liquids, maintaining good durability even after prolonged exposure to sunlight. The superhydrophobic properties could be entirely restored through simple methods, such as steam ironing the fabrics for 3–5 min or oven drying at 70°C for 30 min, showcasing the coating's remarkable self-healing ability. This phenomenon was attributed to the migration and refolding of ODA chains from the interstices of the fabric fibers.

Zhang et al. [77] used polymer stabilizer butyl acrylate (BA) grafted on cellulose nanocrystals (BA-g-CNCs) to achieve a stabilized emulsion with hydrophobic properties. The emulsion was deposited on pre-treated cotton via the pad-dip method. The unmodified CNCs are highly agglomerated and have an uneven particle size distribution due to their high hydrophilicity. The ester exchange reaction was conducted between BA and the surface hydroxyl groups of CNCs to create a stabilized emulsion. The achieved WCA was 97° . The coating improved the mechanical properties of the cotton.

Starch

Starch serves as the principal carbohydrate reserve within plants, primarily accumulating in structures such as tubers and seed endosperms. Comprising a blend of two essential glucans, namely, amylose and amylopectin, starch also contains trace quantities of proteins and lipids. This intricate composition grants starch its fundamental role in storing energy and nourishment. Starch finds its most prevalent sources in crops like corn and rice, where it assumes a pivotal role in sustaining the plant's growth and development. Starch exhibits a remarkable property of insolubility in cold water, alcohol, and ether, contributing to its stability and longevity [82]. At a specific temperature, when subjected to heating, the molecular kinetic energy reaches a threshold that enables it to surmount the intermolecular hydrogen bonds within the core of the starch granule. The temperature range within which starch gelatinization occurs commences with the initial signs of granule swelling and concludes when nearly 100% of the granules have undergone gelatinization. In instances where granular integrity is compromised, such as through the dry grinding of starch, gelatinization becomes more readily achievable, potentially even in cool water. Granules that have been damaged exhibit heightened reactivity to both chemicals and enzymes [83]. Starch is a promising material due to its low cost, excellent film-forming ability, extensive sources, biocompatibility, renewability, and biodegradability. Because of its hydrophilicity, its use is limited. Esterification, etherification, crosslinking, grafting, and condensing reactions are commonly used to improve their water-repellent properties [84]. Figure 12 presents the molecular structure of starch.

Figure 12. Chemical structure of starch.

Milionis et al. [85] employed the hydrophobic properties of thermoplastic starch composite for using lycopodium (natural powder material derived from the spores of lycopodium plants) nanoparticles as an alternative to silica nanoparticles and achieved WCA of 106° for aluminum substrates. Despite not being used on textiles, it is a good example of the replacement of synthetic materials with natural alternatives.

Mahmud et al. [86] modified starch using citric acid as both an esterifying and crosslinking agent as an environmental and cheaper solution. The study focused on employing jute as the substrate. To enhance solution flexibility and viscosity, glycerin was introduced as a plasticizer. The resulting coating was manually applied to the substrate using a knife-coating technique. An absorbency test showed prolonged time when compared untreated cotton with treated one. The water droplet of untreated cotton was completely absorbed in 3 min and the time for the treated one was 9 min. The solubility test showed that the starch started to dissolve after 24 h of immersion in water. The samples without glycerin exhibited the smallest weight loss. The authors attributed this phenomenon to the introduction of glycerin, which potentially disrupted the bonding strength between coating molecules. This effect was likely influenced by glycerin's inherent water solubility, further contributing to its impact on the coating's behavior.

Cationic starch was used in layer-by-layer self-assembly open coating in the research of Forsman et al. [12] and was already described in chapter Section 5.1.1 Natural waxes.

Chitosan

CS is a cationic polysaccharide and is produced by the deacetylation of chitin [87]. It is the second most abundant biopolymer in nature following cellulose and exhibits its presence across a diverse array of eukaryotic species, including crustaceans, insects, and fungi. Comprising a polymer of N-acetyl-D-glucosamine, the solubility of chitosan in water is intricately linked to its molecular weight (MW), where a lower MW translates to heightened water solubility. Chitosan's solubility in water manifests distinctly based on its MW. When the MW of chitosan surpasses the 30 kDa threshold, the protonation of its amino group necessitates the presence of an acid to facilitate dissolution in water. Among these acids, acetic acid emerges as the foremost choice for this purpose. However, an assortment of other naturally occurring acids within the human body, such as HCl, lactic acid, citric acid, and pyruvic acid, are also capable of solubilizing chitosan in water, with the notable exception of phosphoric acid [88]. A subject of escalating interest in recent years, the antimicrobial efficacy of chitosan has garnered significant attention across various categories of microorganisms. This pronounced antimicrobial activity underscores chitosan's potential as a versatile agent with implications spanning diverse applications [89]. There are two options for superhydrophobic modification of textiles with chitosan. One

option is using manipulation to achieve adequate nanoparticle sizes as well as the roughness topography. The second option is a chemical modification of the amine group that allows for the control of the stability of nanoparticles in dispersion and wettability of the final coating [87].

Roy et al. [90] developed a superhydrophobic coating by combining chitosan amines modified with octadecylamine (ODA), a long-chain polymer. CS, used in this study, was synthesized from discarded crab shells. Glutaraldehyde (GA) served as a crosslinking agent. During the grafting reaction, a reticulate effect occurred among the amine groups of ODA, CS, and the carbonyl groups of GA. This facilitated significant enhancements in physical, mechanical, chemical, and microbiological resistance properties. The application of the coating was carried out on standard surgical-grade cotton, which had been pre-treated with oxygen plasma, utilizing a spray method with a pen gun. The resulting coating achieved WCA of up to 159° . It demonstrated good washing durability. The coating exhibited resilience against sandpaper abrasion and tape peel tests with only a minor reduction in its superhydrophobic characteristics. Intriguingly, any decline in superhydrophobic performance could be fully restored by a simple ironing process for 2 min, underscoring a reversible effect. The coating also showcased self-cleaning properties against dust and various liquids.

Joshi et al. [9] used CS known for its polycationic properties, and poly(sodium-4-styrene sulfonate) (PSS), an effective anionic polyelectrolyte via the LBL self-assembly technique. The deposition of up to 20 bilayers was feasible, but notably, the peak of optimal coating performance was reached at 12 bilayers, resulting in a distinctive WCA of 90° . Upon close examination of the results, the study revealed a marginal reduction in the air permeability of the fabric in the 10-bilayer samples. However, the inherent flexibility and tactile characteristics of the original material remained largely unchanged. The coating also exhibited antibacterial activity.

Suryaprabha et al. [91] developed an antibacterial and superhydrophobic composite coating based on chitin–polyaniline (PAni) with the incorporation of metal oxides. Polyaniline (PAni), known for its excellent conductivity and synergistic properties when combined with chitin, played a pivotal role in this research. The resulting chitosan–PAni–ZnO–STA coating exhibited a distinctive binary (micro-/nano-)morphology. Initially, the WCA of the cotton was only 7° with the chitosan–PAni coating, which improved significantly to 90° after the deposition of ZnO. Further enhancement of the hydrophobicity occurred after the deposition of STA. The SA of the chitosan–PAni–ZnO–STA is 8° , underscoring its self-cleaning properties. The micro-/nano-scale roughness of the superhydrophobic cotton surface minimized water droplet adhesion, allowing water droplets to easily roll off. Durability tests indicated that the superhydrophobic properties of the coating were retained after abrasion resistance test, but not after chemical durability and washing test. Additionally, continuous exposure to UV radiation was found to affect the stability of the superhydrophobic coating on the cotton surface.

Raeisi and colleagues [92] used a method where they immersed cotton in a solution comprising CS dissolved in acidic water and glycerol, followed by immersion in the same solution enriched with TiO_2 nanoparticles. The concentration of these nanoparticles had a significant impact on the WCA as cotton coated solely with chitosan exhibited a WCA of 62° . The introduction of TiO_2 nanoparticles at a concentration of 7 wt% resulted in an increase in the WCA, reaching 161° , accompanied by a sliding angle of 5° . The relationship between the WCA and SA with the concentration of TiO_2 is illustrated in Figure 13, showing that higher WCA yields lower SA. Morphological analysis revealed that the nanoparticles comprehensively covered the fabric's surface, leading to the formation of a densely packed nano-scale structure. The coating demonstrated good chemical durability. The coated cotton

exhibited substantial UV protection capabilities, attributed to the high UV absorbance and scattering properties of TiO₂ nanostructures primarily concentrated at the surface layer of the coatings. Furthermore, the coating displayed antibacterial activity.

Figure 13. Relationship between WCA and SA.

Xue et al. [93] used CS, amino carbon nanotubes (ACNTs) to create nano-micro surface roughness, and octadecylamine (ODA) to lower the surface energy. CS-ACNTs-ODA is a photothermal and superhydrophobic coating that was deposited on cotton fabrics. Cotton fabric was submerged into the sonicated solution. The coating achieved a WCA of 160° and SA of 7°. The coated cotton fabric also proved effective for rapid deicing. Furthermore, it exhibited a separation efficacy of over 91%. The fabric displayed excellent abrasion durability. The coated fabric demonstrated stability during the first 50 washes. However, continuous washing eventually caused the coating to peel off from the fabric’s surface.

Table 4. A summary of studies that fabricated hydrophobic textile coating using polysaccharides, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	CNCs, CESO, HDTS, dip-coating	WCA (CESO treatment) = 115°, WCA (CESO + CNC treatment) = 143°, WCA (CESO + CNCs + HDTS) = 157°, water/oil separation efficiency = 98%, 5 different sites per sample	N/A	CD (water, decane, DMF, H ₂ SO ₄ , NaOH; one week)—WCA > 150°	[80]
100% cotton	CNCs, CS, pad-dry method	WCA = 135°	MP break at strength (CS/CNCs 0.5 wt%) = +21% (CS/CNCs 1 wt%) = +10%; elongation at break (CS/CNCs, 0.5 wt%) = +26%, (CS/CNCs 1 wt%) = +17%	WD (AATCC 183 [94]) = 130–135°	[78]

Table 4. Cont.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	CNFs, ODA, spraying, chemical grafting	WCA = 152 (± 3) $^\circ$, 5 different sites per sample	MP tensile strength = +3%; young modulus = +13%, self-cleaning (methyl red, methyl orange, methylene blue), self-healing (steam ironing for 3–5 min or oven drying at 70 $^\circ$ C for 30 min)	WD (vigorously stirring in lukewarm soapy water, 50 $^\circ$ C, 30 min, thorough rinsing, drying in ambient T, after 30 cycles)—WCA = 134 $^\circ$, AR (rubbing on a ceramic tile), after 500 cycles)—WCA = 145 $^\circ$, natural sunlight exposure test (31 days, 5 h per day exposure on the sun)—WCA = 148 $^\circ$	[81]
100% cotton	CNFs, butyl acrylate, dip-pad, grafting (esterification)	WCA = 97 (± 6) $^\circ$, 3 different sites per sample	MP elongation at break = +17%; breaking tenacity = +20%	N/A	[77]
100% jute	corn starch, citric acid, glycerol, esterification, crosslinking, manual “knife” coating	water absorption test: time increased from 3 to 9 min	MP bending length (warp) = +20%, (weft) = +22%	CD (water, 24 h)—weight loss 31–45%	[86]
surgical grade cotton	CS, octadecylamine, glutaraldehyde, grafting, spraying	WCA = 159 (± 3) $^\circ$, 6 different sites per sample	self-cleaning property (against dust and liquids), self-healing (if hot-pressed)	WD (lukewarm detergent, 50 $^\circ$ C, 60 cycles)—WCA = 159 $^\circ$ (± 3), (lukewarm detergent, 50 $^\circ$ C, 80 cycles) — WCA = 127 $^\circ$, AR (sandpaper test, 55 cycles)—WCA = 159 (± 3) $^\circ$	[90]
100% cotton	CS, poly(sodium-4-styrene sulfonate), layer-by-layer self-assembly	WCA = 90 (± 8)	AP (CS + PSS) = –24%, ANT. P. (<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>) = 97.5%	N/A	[9]
100% cotton	CS, PAni, ZnO, STA, immersion	WCA (chitosan + PaNi + ZnO + STA) = 154 $^\circ$, SA = 5 $^\circ$, WCA (CS+ PaNi + ZnO) = 90 $^\circ$, WCA (chitosan + PaNi) = 104 $^\circ$, water/oil separation = 97.8%, 3 different sites per sample	self-cleaning against dust: SA = 8 $^\circ$, ANTI. P. (<i>S. aureus</i>) = 0.7 mm, (<i>E. coli</i>) = 1 mm.	WD (45 min, room T, 10 cycles)—WCA = 125 $^\circ$, CD (acid, alkali, 24 h)—WCA = 135 $^\circ$, AR (sandpaper test, 13 cycles)—WCA = 153 $^\circ$, (peeling test, after 50 cycles)—WCA = 151 $^\circ$	[91]
100% cotton	CS, TiO ₂ , immersion	WCA (CS) = 62 $^\circ$, WCA (CS, 1 wt% TiO ₂) = 75 $^\circ$, (CS, 3 wt% TiO ₂) = 123 $^\circ$, SA(CS, 3 wt% TiO ₂) = 60 $^\circ$, WCA (CS, 5 wt% TiO ₂) = 140 $^\circ$, SA(CS, 5 wt% TiO ₂) = 25 $^\circ$, WCA(CS, 7 wt% TiO ₂) = 161 $^\circ$, SA(chitosan, 7 wt% TiO ₂) = 5 $^\circ$	anti. P. (<i>E.coli</i>) = 99.8%, (<i>S. aureus</i>) = 97.3%	CD (NaOH, HCl, 96 h)—WCA = 151 $^\circ$	[92]

Table 4. Cont.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	CS, ACNTs, ODA, immersion	WCA = 160°, SA 7°	self-cleaning (tested with quartz sand), photothermal performance, deicing performance	WD (immersion in warm soapy water, 50 °C, 700 rpm, 30 min, air-dried for 24 h)—WCA = 151°, SA = 11° AR (sandpaper, 50 cycles) WCA > 150°, SA = 7–12°, (tape stripping test, 80 cycles)—WCA = 154°, SA = 11°	[93]

5.2.2. Proteins

Proteins, as macromolecules, are ubiquitous in a wide array of living systems, ranging from bacteria and viruses to unicellular and simple eukaryotic organisms, even extending to complex vertebrates and higher mammals, including humans. They showcase a universal presence and hold a remarkable position in biological entities. Accounting for over 50% of the cellular dry weight, proteins surpass other biomolecules in terms of abundance. Notably unique among macromolecules, proteins play a pivotal role by acting as the fundamental catalyst for all biochemical reactions within biological systems [95]. Proteins exhibit intricate structures, forming a linear sequence of amino acid residues that tightly intertwine to create a polypeptide chain. Comprising carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and oxygen, as fundamental components, amino acids serve as the cornerstone of protein architecture [95,96]. The bonds between amino acids create a crystalline lattice through charged interactions, resulting in robust forces that contribute to higher melting and boiling points. These charged groups also induce electrical conductivity in aqueous solutions, granting amino acids electrolytic properties. Their notable solubility in water and the significant dipole moment inherent in crystalline matter further emphasize their nature as charged entities crystallizing from solutions containing dipolar ions. Amino acids unite through peptide bonds, where one molecule's amino group harmoniously reacts with another's carboxyl group, a chemical connection known as condensation. This process liberates water as a byproduct and gives rise to a dipeptide entity. In a broader context, the ionization tendencies of constituent amino acids, including those within their side chains, significantly influence the solubility, stability, and architectural arrangement of proteins. Simultaneously, these side chains' hydrophobic and hydrophilic characteristics play pivotal roles in governing the physicochemical dynamics of polypeptide chains, orchestrating their precise folding into intricate three-dimensional configurations [95,96]. A summary of the studies that used proteins can be found in Table 5. In Figure 14, the molecular structures of zein and casein are presented.

Figure 14. Examples of the molecular structures of proteins (zein and casein).

Kim et al. [97] conducted research where they tested different proteins (casein, bovine serum albumin) in combination with flavonoids. The best results were achieved with bovine serum albumin (in combination with lacasse), achieving a WCA of 137°, while casein lowered the WCA. More about this research is written in Section Flavonoids.

Zeins

Zein proteins are a group of storage proteins found in corn (maize) kernels. These proteins make up a significant portion of the protein content in corn and serve as a source of nutrition for the developing embryo within the seed. Zein proteins are notable for their unique properties, including their solubility in alcohol (ethanol) rather than water [98].

Gonçalves et al. [10] employed zein (in free form and the form of particles) dissolved in ethanol as a coating agent to enhance cotton textile properties. They conducted a comparative analysis among the following three distinct coating methods: depletion, dropwise impregnation, and padding. The increase in ethanol concentration had a significant impact, reducing the water drop absorption time and resulting in enhanced protein deposition on the cotton textile's surface. This led to the formation of a more substantial and hydrophobic film, with the most favorable outcomes observed when using the highest zein concentration in the free form via the padding method. The authors concluded that this improved performance could be attributed to zein's ability to create a thin, cohesive layer that fills the gaps between fibers, thereby reinforcing the textile structure and imparting hydrophobic characteristics. Across all tested concentrations, all samples exhibited a hydrophobic nature, with contact angles of 90° or greater. However, after 180 s, only the sample with the highest concentration of zein and lowest concentration of ethanol (prepared using the padding method) maintained its hydrophobic WCA. Moreover, the zein coating positively influenced the mechanical properties of the warp, resulting in increased breaking strength compared to the control. This improvement was possibly due to reduced elongation caused by stronger cohesive forces between the fibers. Factors such as fiber shrinkage and increased fabric density may have contributed to this enhancement. On the other hand, the breaking strength of the weft decreased, potentially due to higher inter-fiber friction resistance caused by zein deposition, which limited elongation by filling inter-fiber spaces and increasing fabric rigidity. The results of abrasion and domestic washing tests demonstrated robust durability for the optimal coating described above. Air permeability assessments indicated a marginal reduction in values for treated samples compared to

untreated ones, ranging from 2% to 9%. However, this decrease remained within acceptable limits, ensuring sample comfort by maintaining satisfactory air permeability.

Zhang et al. [99] also used zein (in combination with resin) in their study, which is further described in Section Resin.

Milk Proteins

Both caseins and whey proteins have already been used in hydrophobic coatings for natural textiles. Caseins are the most abundant proteins in milk, composing 80% of the total protein. The second most abundant are whey proteins. They are precipitated from raw milk at pH 4.6 at 20 °C. All caseins contain sites of phosphorylation with a unique sequence. It is insoluble in water. Like most proteins, including whey protein, casein can denature and lose its structure and functionality at temperatures higher than 120 °C [100].

Liu and colleagues [70] created protein gel using the caseinate dispersion method, utilizing milk proteins, calcium caseinate, and whey protein isolates, with the addition of finely crushed ice. This transformation resulted in a reduction in water absorption by the fibers due to the coverage of their surface by protein molecules. The coating was deposited on flax fibers, which decreased the water uptake, reducing it by half from the initial 3.7% observed in untreated fabric. The authors suggest that this reduction is attributed to specific functional groups within the protein molecules, such as methanol groups, which may engage in reactions with hydroxyl groups present in the lignocellulosic fibers, forming covalent bonds that resist water penetration. Additionally, certain groups within the protein molecules, such as amine and amide groups, can form hydrogen bonds with cellulose, further diminishing the fabric's water-absorbing properties. Further analysis of the inherent properties revealed a slight decrease in the tensile strength and improved flexibility.

Hydrophobins

Hydrophobins, proteins synthesized by fungi, are distinguished by their compact molecular structure. These proteins are primarily situated on the external surfaces of fungal fruiting bodies, serving a crucial function in maintaining the dryness of the fungi by reducing the surface tension of their growth medium. A defining characteristic of hydrophobin proteins is the presence of eight conserved cysteine residues, which are arranged in a distinctive pattern. As a result, hydrophobins possess the capacity to exert an influence on the wettability of various other substrates beyond fungi. Interestingly, the changes depend on the initial wetting properties of a substrate [101].

Opwis et al. [102] employed hydrophobins in conjunction with the thermal deposition technique to enhance the hydrophobic properties of textile materials, leveraging the unique bifunctional molecular structure of hydrophobins. A treatment with a 5% hydrophobin solution rendered hydrophilic cotton substrates hydrophobic, exhibiting a water absorption time of 50 min. The capillary decreased from 55 mm for untreated cotton to 2 mm. The treatment withstands at least a typical textile laundry process and a harsh extraction procedure.

Amino Acids

Research has shown that amino acids themselves can also increase the WCA. Grethe et al. [103] explored the application of three distinct hydrophobic amino acids (valine, leucine, and phenylalanine) for wet finishing treatments on cotton and linen fabrics. These amino acids were effectively dissolved within an ammonia solution of pH 11, with their concentrations progressively increased. The uppermost concentration utilized corresponded to the solubility limit. Application of these solutions onto the textile materials was accomplished using a padding technique. Although the achievement of hydrophobic contact angles was not realized, this outcome represents a promising initial phase for the advance-

ment of environmentally friendly finishing agents. The application of 60 g/L of valine resulted in a prolonged soaking time from 10 s to 40 s. Furthermore, the use of 300 g/L of leucine led to an even more substantial increase in the contact angle, surpassing the soaking 60 s.

Naturally Occurring Enzymes

Naturally occurring enzymes are proteins produced by living organisms that act as biological catalysts, accelerating specific biochemical reactions without being consumed or altered in the process. They are found abundantly in nature, including within organisms such as plants, animals, fungi, and microorganisms [104].

Lysozymes and proteases are enzymes that have been already used for hydrophobic coatings. Lysosomes consist of soluble and transmembrane proteins that are directed to these organelles through signal-dependent processes [105]. One of the most promising approaches to achieving hydrophobic surfaces with protein is a lysozyme phase transition. The phase-transited lysozymes can firmly attach to metals, oxides, semiconductors, and polymers [17].

Zhang et al. [106] developed a novel supramolecular assembly approach that involved utilizing phase-transited lysozyme (PTL) and tannic acid (TA) through a simple padding and drying method. TA exhibits the capacity to interact with proteins via non-covalent bindings, including electrostatic interactions, hydrogen bonding, and hydrophobic interactions. The samples were immersed in the freshly prepared PTL/TA solution. This process entailed two dips and two rollings, followed by drying. Additionally, cotton fabric was modified with 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate (MPTES). As a result, the WCA achieved a value of 135°. The PTL/TA coating significantly enhanced the textile's antibacterial properties and also improved UV resistance and antioxidant capabilities.

Protease, also known as peptidase or proteinase, is an enzyme that breaks down proteins into smaller peptides or amino acids by catalyzing the hydrolysis of peptide bonds. They regulate the fate, localization, and activity of many proteins, modulate protein-protein interactions, create new bioactive molecules, contribute to the processing of cellular information, and generate, transduce, and amplify molecular signals [107].

Cheng et al. [108] employed a natural papain enzyme extracted from papaya fruit to etch silk fabric, enhancing its surface roughness. Firstly, the samples were immersed in papain solution. Following the etching process, the fabrics underwent a modification with methyl trichlorosilane (MTCS) through a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) procedure. The resulting samples exhibited a WCA of 154° and an SA of 9°. In addition to papain, another alkaline protease was utilized in the study, capable of not only creating surface roughness but also hydrolyzing the fabric, leading to a remarkable WCA of 157°. Wool subjected to the same treatment showed a WCA of 152° and self-cleaning abilities. This treatment exhibited durability with a sustained high level of hydrophobicity. The protective coating exhibited resilience, enduring two washing cycles while maintaining superhydrophobic contact angles. However, after five cycles, noticeable damage was observed, possibly due to the alkaline substances present in the soap affecting the grafted silane on the fabric surface. Chemical stability tests at high concentrations of alkali, salt, and acid solution showed a reduction in WCA, especially in acidic pH. The air permeability of the fabric increased after the etching process, attributed to surface damage. However, after silane treatment, air permeability decreased. As for mechanical properties, tensile stress, elongation at break, and bending modulus, all experienced a decrease.

Liu et al. [70] used lipase in combination with vegetable oil, as already described in Section 5.1.2.

Table 5. Summary of studies that fabricated a hydrophobic textile coating using proteins, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	zein nanoparticles, ethanol, depletion, impregnation by dropwise addition, impregnation by padding	WCA > 90°, 5 different sites per sample	MP breaking strength (warp) = +15, (weft) = −36%; stretching (warp) = +36%, (weft) = +33%, AP = −2–9%	WD 4/5 (on a greyscale from 1–5), TD degradation at 800 °C, AR 4/5 (on a greyscale from 1–5)	[10]
100% flax	milk proteins isolates, calcium caseinate isolates, whey protein isolates, biocomposite mixture with fibers	water uptake = 1.8% in 500 min	MP tensile strength = −7%, strain at break = +12%	N/A	[70]
100% cotton	hydrophobins, immersion, thermal composition technique	WCA > 90°, drop penetration time = 50 min	N/A	WD (linitester, 40 °C, 30 min, 10 steel balls, ECE laundry detergent 4.0 g/L, V¼150 mL, extraction: soxhlet, ethanol/water 50/50 vol.%, 4 h)—withstand at least 1 washing cycle and 1 extraction method	[102]
100% weaved wool, 100% knitted and weaved cotton	PTL, TA, MP TES, DTSAC, pad-dry method, grafting, sol-gel	WCA = 135°	N/A	WD—withstand 50 cycles, AR—withstand 100 rubbing cycles	[106]
100% silk, 100% wool (only treatment with alkaline protease)	papain (papaya enzyme), alkaline protease, MTCS, etching, chemical vapor deposition (MTCS)	WCA (PA + MTCS) = 154°, WCA (MTCS) = 110°, WCA (PA, alkaline protease) = 157°, WCA(alkaline protease on wool) = 152°, 3 different sites per sample	MP tensile stress (PA etched, warp) = −18%, (PA + MTCS, warp) = −26%, (PA etched, weft) = −14%, (PA + MTCS, weft) = 14%, elongation at break (PA etched, warp) = −14%, (PA + MTCS, warp) = −14%, (PA etched, weft) = −83%, (PA + MTCS, weft) = −83%, elongation at break (PA etched, warp) = +17%, (PA + MTCS, warp) = −3%, (PA etched, weft) = +30% gf cm ² /cm, (PA + MTCS, warp) = −3%, AP (PA etched) = +4%, (PA + MTCS) = −7%, self-cleaning ability	WD (AACC 61-2006 [94])—WCA (silk, 2 cycles) = 150°, WCA (silk, 9 cycles) = 140° AR (pristine silk fabric as abraiser, 100 cycles)—WCA (silk) = 154°	[108]

5.2.3. Complex Aromatic Biopolymers

Complex aromatic biopolymers possess intricate and elaborate molecular structures, distinguished by the presence of aromatic rings in their backbone. These biopolymers play integral roles across a spectrum of biological systems, exhibiting diverse functions within living organisms [109]. For the hydrophobicity of textiles, lignin is most often used. A summary of studies using complex aromatic biopolymers can be found in Table 6.

Table 6. A summary of a study that fabricated hydrophobic textile coating using complex aromatic biopolymer, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	beeswax, lignin, N-hexane, spray coating	WCA = 150°, 5 different sites per sample	N/A	TD (120 °C, 60 min)—WCA > 135°, CD (acid, alkali solutions)—WCA = 150°, does not withstand prolonged immersion	[60]

Lignin

Lignin stands out as the most prevalent naturally occurring aromatic polymer. It forms a crucial component of plant cell walls, conferring both structural stability and aiding in the regulation of water movement. Lignin is commercially available largely as a byproduct of industrial processes, particularly within the paper and pulp sector, lignin finds some utilization as a low-value energy resource. Its occurrence within lignocellulosic raw materials varies, ranging from 10% to 35%, contingent upon the specific source. Comprising mainly aromatic alcohols—p-coumaric, coniferyl, and sinapyl—lignin’s distinguishing characteristic rests upon the count of methoxy groups. As methoxy groups increase in number, the propensity for crosslinking is enhanced [109]. Notably, the inherent properties of lignin contribute to a heightened WCA as evidenced by a study conducted by Borrega et al. [110], where lignin films without additives achieved WCA 43–58°.

Zhang et al. [60] developed coating from beeswax and lignin was applied onto a cotton substrate, effectively creating a material capable of separating water and oil. The fabrication process involved heating beeswax and lignin at 100 °C for 20 min until the beeswax was completely liquefied. To ensure uniformity, N-hexane was introduced by spraying to create a consistent suspension. Beeswax and lignin contributed to the material’s low surface energy and micro-/nano-scale structures, respectively. It is noteworthy that porous materials with a large lignin content need more surface coverage density to obtain superhydrophobic properties as the hydroxyl groups in the chemical structure of lignin increase the surface energy of the whole film. The treatment maintained the original fibrous morphologies of the cotton. The authors established the robust stability of hydrophobic material, as evidenced by the enduring contact angle of approximately 150° even when exposed to strong acid or alkali solutions. This phenomenon was attributed to the micro-/nano-structures that effectively entrapped air within the coating. The presence of lignin within the formulation enhanced the material’s thermal stability. Furthermore, the porous nature of the developed material facilitated easy recycling through reactivation, adding to its eco-friendliness and sustainability.

5.2.4. Other Natural Polymers

In Figure 15 the molecular structure of natural rubber and resin are presented. A summary of studies using other natural polymers like NRL and rosin can be found in Table 7.

Figure 15. Molecular structure of resin and natural rubber.

Natural Rubber

Natural rubber is a type of rubber that is derived from the sap of rubber trees, primarily *Hevea brasiliensis* [111]. Natural rubber particles are located in the milk cells and are found in tiny vessels in the inner cortex of the tree bark, which is below the outer cortex. Natural rubber latex (NRL) is acknowledged as a colloidal dispersion primarily composed of rubber particles enveloped by a delicate coating of proteins, lipids, and extensive strands of fatty acids. This intricate arrangement imparts a negative charge to the particles, thereby guaranteeing the colloidal stability of the medium. To counteract its inherent propensity for swift degradation and coagulation, NRL is commonly fortified through the introduction of chemical agents [112]. Some of the key advantages of natural rubber is its elasticity and flexibility, which make it ideal for use in products that require high levels of resilience and durability [113].

Tao et al. [11] effectively harnessed the eco-friendly potential of waterborne NRL in conjunction with in situ synthesized gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). They accomplished the integration of these nanoparticles by controlled heating. Subsequently, they strategically adhered the resulting hybrid material onto cotton textile surfaces using a precise “dip and dry” technique, resulting in a substantial increase in surface roughness. The textiles treated with this material displayed significantly prolonged absorption times for water, milk, and coffee, exceeding 30 min. The treatment’s effectiveness continued to improve with each successive cycle, notably shifting from an initial hydrophilic state to a hydrophobic one by the sixth cycle. WCA values exhibited remarkable enhancement in cycles 7, 8, and 9, ultimately reaching WCAs of 132°, 133°, and 133°, respectively.

Banerjee et al. [114] innovatively crafted an antimicrobial and hydrophobic coating material based on NRL. NRL was crosslinked through the application of “thiol-ene chemistry”, using trimethylolpropane tris(3-mercaptopropionate) (trithiol) as a crosslinker and Irgacure-184 as a photoinitiator under UV irradiation. This process enabled the production of antimicrobial cotton fibers through dip coating and curing. Before coating the cotton fiber with NRL and undergoing the curing process, it was blended with Ag NPs modified chitosan. The integration of Ag NPs within the cured NRL coating rendered the cotton fabric hydrophobic, achieving a WCA of 102°. This coating significantly increased the elongation at breakage by up to 25%. The presence of NRL within the microfibrillar structure of the cotton fiber imparted elasticity to the fiber, thereby enhancing its elongation capabilities. Additionally, the stress at the breaking point was as well enhanced.

Resin

Zhang et al. [99] undertook a study to impart hydrophobic properties to cotton fabric through a straightforward immersion process involving the following two natural polymers: zein (Section Zeins) and rosin. Rosin, a natural resin derived from pine trees, boasts an inherent hydrophobic nature owing to its composition, primarily consisting of resin acids (90%). Its low surface energy arises from a hydrophobic hydrogenated phenanthrene ring

structure, similar to that of long-chain aliphatic compounds. Compared to cotton fabric treated solely with zein, the introduction of the zein-rosin complex led to a notable increase in the WCA from 120° to 133°. This enhancement can be attributed to the creation of a rougher fabric surface. The roughness arises from the orientation of hydrophobic zein groups in higher ethanol concentrations, causing negatively charged particles to repel each other and form nanospheres. The zein-rosin complex formed more intricate and stable aggregates, which readily adhered to the fiber surface. The treated cotton fabrics demonstrated commendable antibacterial activity. Importantly, these functional fabrics maintained their mechanical properties and even exhibited increased air permeability, a rather uncommon outcome. This improvement can be attributed to the formation of a hydrophobic film on the surface of the zein or zein-rosin-treated cotton fabrics, which endowed them with a low surface energy. Consequently, the coefficient of friction between the fibers decreased, reducing surface tension and rendering the cotton fibers fluffier and silkier, facilitating enhanced air passage through the functionalized cotton fabric. Additionally, the WVTP also improved.

Table 7. Summary of studies that fabricated hydrophobic textile coating using other natural polymers (NRL nads rosin), N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
cotton	NRL, AuNPs, dip-dry	WCA (NRL, AuNP, 7 coating layers) = 132°, WCA (NRL, AuNP, 8 coating layers) = 133°, WCA (NRL, AuNP, 9 coating layers) = 133°; oil–water separation-efficiency = 96%	N/A	N/A	[11]
cotton	NRL, AgNP, dip-dry	WCA (NRL, AgNP) = 102°, 3 samples per set	MP elongation at break (NRL, AgNP) = +23, stress at break (NRL, AgNP) = +53%, ANTI P. against Gram-negative and positive bacteria	N/A	[114]
mercerized bleached (100%) pure cotton	zein, rosin, ethanol, immersion	WCA (zein) = 120 (±3)°, WCA (zein-rosin) = 133 (±2.5)°, 5 different sites per sample	MP breaking strength (zein) = +7%, (zein-rosin) treated = +2%, AP (zein) = +4%, (zein-rosin) = +11%; WVTP (zein treated) = −3% (zein-rosin) treated = +5%, ANTI. P. (<i>E. coli</i>) = 92.2%, (<i>S. aureus</i>) = 87.2%	WD (GB/T 8629-2017 [115])—WCA, 5 cycles) = 115 (±2)°, AR (GB/T 3920-2008 [116], after 300 cycles) = 119 (±3)°	[99]

5.3. Naturally Occurring Compounds

Naturally occurring compounds are chemical substances obtained directly from the environment, in their natural state, or with minimal processing. These compounds are produced by various living organisms, including plants, animals, fungi, and microorganisms, and they play diverse roles in the biological and ecological systems of our planet. A summary of studies using naturally occurring compounds can be found in Table 8. Figure 16 presents two examples of naturally occurring compounds.

Figure 16. Examples of molecular structures of naturally occurring compounds.

5.3.1. Betulin

One of the naturally occurring compounds that is known to have hydrophobic properties is betulin. It is a solvent extracted from the outer bark of several species of trees. Betulin has very low surface energy due to its hydrocarbon skeleton. An especially known tree containing betulin is birch, which represents the main component [117]. The following studies demonstrate the potential utilization of betulin, a byproduct derived from the forest industry, in a range of value-added applications.

Huang et al. [117] functionalized cellulose involving oxidation using TEMPO, followed by the covalent attachment of betulin through esterification. The WCA achieved a value of 136° , which can be attributed to the presence of CH groups within betulin that contributed to a lower surface energy. A higher degree of esterification was linked to a heightened level of hydrophobicity. The material exhibited remarkable antibacterial capabilities. The oxidation process significantly reduced the mechanical properties of the textiles, particularly their tensile strength.

Huang et al. [118] impregnated cellulosic textiles with two different betulin-based solutions. A solution containing betulin and ethanol achieved a WCA of 153° . When cotton was treated with a betulin–terephthaloyl chloride (TPC) copolymer in tetrahydrofuran with an excess of pyridine, the cotton fabric displayed a WCA of 151° . Additionally, films were prepared using betulin and betulin–TPC copolymer, which were then coated onto the fabric surface using a solvent casting/compression molding technique. The resulting coated fabrics exhibited WCAs of 123° and 104° , respectively. These coating solutions lack durability, as they cannot withstand laundering, and the coating (specifically betulin) begins to wash away during the spray test.

5.3.2. Melanin

Melanin is a ubiquitous biological pigment found in all living species. It plays crucial biological roles in living organisms by providing photoprotection, antibacterial, metal-chelating, antioxidation, and free radical scavenging abilities [119].

Pakdel et al. [119] harnessed the unique properties of melanin to enhance cotton fabrics with a remarkable combination of attributes: superhydrophobicity, UV protection, and personalized thermal management through the photothermal effect. This improvement was achieved through a surface modification process, involving the application of coatings composed of natural melanin (NM) particles extracted from yak hair and a fluorine-free polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) polymer, utilizing a dip-pad-dry-cure technique. The outcomes of the research demonstrated the effectiveness of NM/PDMS coatings characterized by WCA of 164° . Intriguingly, the best results were obtained with the smallest amount of

melanin applied (0.05%). Moreover, the NM/PDMS coating substantially enhanced the thermal stability of the cotton substrate and maintained their water vapor transmission capability, indicating that the coatings exclusively covered the surface of fibers without obstructing the fabric's natural pores. The mechanical properties, including breaking forces and flexural rigidity, remained intact after the deposition of these coatings. Furthermore, the coated fabrics exhibited outstanding breathability and displayed good abrasion and washing durability.

5.3.3. Phytic Acid

Phytic acid (PA) is a polyphosphoric acid, a class of compounds characterized by the presence of multiple phosphoric acid groups ($-\text{PO}(\text{OH})_2$) in their molecular structure. It is an extract from plants known for its primary role as a phosphorus reservoir. It is an antinutrient compound and occurs in most cereal grains, legumes, nuts, oilseeds, tubers, pollen, spores, and organic soils [120]. PA can effectively bind toxic mineral elements in the human body due to its six phosphate groups. These phosphate groups enable phytic acid to form insoluble coordination complexes with certain metal ions, even at room temperature, promoting the aggregation of these metals into stable complexes.

Zhou et al. [121] developed a PA-FeIII-based superhydrophobic fabric. Firstly, cotton was alternately immersed into phytic acid and FeIII solution using the LBL self-assembly technique. They also tried other metal particles and they all achieved similar results. Afterward so prepared dry cotton fabric was immersed in chloroform solution containing PDMS prepolymer as low-surface-energy material and curing agent. This process yielded a hierarchical micro- and nanostructure on the modified fabric surface, reaching a WCA of $152^\circ (\pm 1.4)^\circ$. The materials exhibited excellent chemical stability and only a slight decrease after abrasion resistance test.

Cheng et al. [122] used PA as a phosphorus precursor and a catalyst for hydrolyzing tetraethoxysilane for deposition on silk fabric via pad-dry technique. Coating using the coupling agent 3-aminopropyltrimethoxymethylsilane (APDTM) achieved WCA 130° and 89° without APDTM. The washing durability test revealed that the modified sol-treated fabrics maintained a WCA above 100° after 7 washing cycles. In terms of physical properties, the tensile strength of the silk fabric decreased by 23% for the unmodified sol treatment and 26% when modified with APDTM.

Xu et al. [69] used PA as an etchant for cotton fabric, a study previously outlined in Section 5.3.2.

5.3.4. Phenolic Compounds

Caffeic Acid

Caffeic acid (3,4-dihydroxycinnamic acid) is a natural phenolic compound commonly found in coffee, fruits, wine, and traditional Chinese medicine. It is known for its excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability [123]. It has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticarcinogenic activities [124].

Zhou et al. [123] prepared superhydrophobic cotton by immersing it in an aqueous solution containing caffeic acid (CfA) and Fe particles. The reaction was catalyzed by laccase. Deposition of caffeic acid/Fe hybrid particles increased the surface roughness of cotton fibers and achieved a high WCA of about 158° . The samples exhibited excellent abrasion durability and self-cleaning properties with oil-water separation efficiency above 99%. Both tensile strength and elongation at break have slightly decreased. CfA/Fe can be deposited on many different substrates.

Flavonoids

Flavonoids, recognized as hydrophobic compounds in scientific literature, present a promising avenue for imbuing natural fibers with hydrophobic properties. These naturally occurring compounds showcase a diverse array of phenolic structures and can be sourced from fruits, vegetables, grains, bark, roots, stems, flowers, tea, and wine. Within the plant kingdom, flavonoids serve essential roles in growth and defense mechanisms against various threats. The exceptional properties of flavonoids encompass their antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, and anticarcinogenic attributes, bolstered by their capacity to influence critical cellular enzyme functions. Structurally, flavonoids encompass a fifteen-carbon skeleton comprising two interconnected benzene rings linked by a heterocyclic pyrane ring. This chemical configuration underscores their bioactivity [125,126]. Researchers are exploring the potential of harnessing flavonoids to render natural fibers hydrophobic, representing an innovative approach in materials science with implications for various practical applications.

Kim & Cavaco et al. [97] incorporated enzymatic conjugation of protein–flavonoids through laccase catalysis, on flax fibers. The cationization process was performed using an anionic polyelectrolyte. The anchoring of these conjugates onto the fibers was achieved by incubating flax fabrics. In this study, various proteins were tested, and the most optimal WCA of 137° was achieved with bovine serum albumin in combination with catechin. This treatment showed good washing stability and significant antioxidant activity (exceeding 93%).

Tannin

Tannins are eco-friendly, bio-sourced, natural, and highly reactive polyphenols. They are a group of aromatic macromolecules. Plant-based polyphenolic tannins are the fourth most abundant group of compounds extracted from terrestrial biomass, following cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin [127]. In plants, they function as defense agents against herbivores, fungi, and microorganisms. Furthermore, they are also present in non-vascular plants, i.e., algae, in which they have various metabolic roles. Tannins can be classified according to their chemical structure into hydrolyzable and condensed tannins. Recently, tannins have been investigated for their interaction with other species to obtain tannin-based hybrid systems with advanced and/or novel properties [127]. For example, Srisod et al. [128] extracted tannin from *Xylocarpus granatum* bark (XGBE) that was used to form insoluble complexes through hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic forces for antimicrobial textile coating. Furthermore, in virtue of the tannins' chemistry and their high reactivity, they either physicochemically or physically interact with a wide variety of different compounds, including metals and ceramics, as well as several organic species [127]. In Figure 17, an example of hydrophobic coating with tannin in combination with laser ablation is presented.

Tian et al. [51] successfully developed a multifunctional cotton fabric with enhanced properties, including directional water transport, superior UV protection, and antibacterial capabilities, through a combination of persimmon tannin (PT) and laser treatment (L). Initially, persimmon tannin was applied to woven cotton, creating a hydrophobic surface and constructing a micro-nano structure with WCA 145°. Subsequently, the PT-treated cotton fabric was laser-dotted for directional water transport through the fabric's thickness which was achieved with a power of 4 W which decreased WCA to 110°. The degree of WCA was influenced by the laser power. As the laser power increased further WCA decreased. Lower laser power affected only the fabric's surface, leaving the back side unaffected. Consequently, the top side exhibited improved wettability, while the back side maintained its hydrophobic property, resulting in a wettability gradient along the fabric's thickness, thereby enabling directional water transport. The treatment does not give good

washing durability results which can be attributed to insufficient bonding between PT and cotton fibers. Moisture and air permeability decreased after PT treatment but improved after laser treatment, likely due to the removal of local hydrophobic substances and the formation of porous structures by laser treatment. The PT-treated cotton fabric exhibited an increase in breaking strength and bending length indicating enhanced resistance to deformation and greater stiffness. The PT-L treated fabric experienced a reduction in strength due to fiber breakage resulting from laser treatment.

Figure 17. Tannin deposition on cotton through immersion followed by laser ablation as described by Tian et al. [51].

Table 8. A summary of studies that fabricated hydrophobic textile coating using naturally occurring compounds, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	betulin, toluene, oxidation, esterification	WCA = 136°, 5 different sites per sample	MP tensile strength, (betulin, toluene) = −93%, elongation at break (betulin, toluene) = −11%, ANT. P. (Gram-positive, Gram-negative) = 99%,	N/A	[117]
100% cotton	(a) betulin + ethanol, (b) betulin-terephthaloyl chloride (TPC) copolymer in tetrahydrofuran, (c) films from betulin, (d) films betulin-TPC copolymer, (a) impregnation, (b) impregnation, (c) solvent casting, (d) solvent casting	WCA (a) = 153°, WCA (b) = 151°, WCA (c) = 123°, WCA (d) = 104°, 5 different sites per sample	N/A	N/A	[118]

Table 8. Cont.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	melanin particles, polydimethylsiloxane (PMDS), dip coating	WCA (0.05%melanin, PMDS) = 164 (± 4) $^{\circ}$, 5 different sites per sample	MP breaking force: (0.05% melanin, PMDS) = +3%, flexural rigidity (0.05% melanin, PMDS) = –2.5%, WVTP (0.05% melanin, PMDS) = +8%	WD (AATCC-61-2010, 5 cycles)—WCA = 160 $^{\circ}$, AR (ASTM D4966-12 2016 [129], 1000 cycles)—WCA = 150 $^{\circ}$, CD (acid, neutral)—WCA = 164 $^{\circ}$, (alkali) = not durable, TD (0.05% melanin, PMDS) +2% (330 $^{\circ}$ C)	[119]
100% cotton	phytic acid, metal ions (AgI, FeIII, CeIII, ZrIV, and SnIV), PDMS, layer by layer self assembly	WCA (PA–FeIII-PDMS) = 152 (± 1) $^{\circ}$, WCA (PDMS) = 114 (± 2) $^{\circ}$, 5 different sites per sample	N/A	CD (ethanol, n-hexane, xylene, acetone, 7 days) WCA > 150 $^{\circ}$, AR (sandpaper 30 cycles)—WCA (mesh 600) = 143 (± 3) $^{\circ}$, WCA (mesh 1000) = 149 (± 1.2) $^{\circ}$, (peeling test, 300 cycles)—WCA = 150 $^{\circ}$	[121]
100% silk	phytic acid(PA) + TEOS + ethanol, APDTM, sol-gel, immersion, pad-dry	WCA (PA) = 83 $^{\circ}$, WCA (APDTM) = 114 $^{\circ}$, WCA (PA +APDTM) = 130 $^{\circ}$, 5 different sites per sample	MP tensile strength (PA-treated silk) = –23% (PA+ APDTM treated silk) = –26%, bending length (PA-treated silk) = +44%, (PA+ APDTM treated silk) = +25% mm, flexular rigidity (PA-treated silk) = +70% (PA+ APDTM treated silk) = +57%	WD (2 g/L commercial detergent, the liquor ratio was 50:1, 40 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min, 9 cycles) = decrease TD (50% weight loss, 456 $^{\circ}$ C) = (PA + APDTM) = +19%,	[122]
100% cotton	caffeic acid, FeSO ₄ , laccase, immersion	WCA = 158 $^{\circ}$, 3 different sites per sample	UV stability	CD (acidic, alkaline liquid, hot water and organic solvents, 6 days): WCA > 150 $^{\circ}$ except NaOH and HCl, UV durability—WCA > 150 $^{\circ}$, AR (ISO105-X12:2001 [130], after 100 cycles) = 149 $^{\circ}$	[123]
100% flax	proteins (bovine serum albumin/casein), laccase, flavonoids (quercetin/cathecin), cationization, oxidation, enzymatic conjugation, incubation	WCA (bovine serum, laccase, flavonoid-catechin) = 137 (± 1) $^{\circ}$, WCA (casein, laccase, flavonoid-catechin) = 48 (± 4) $^{\circ}$, 3 different sites per sample	N/A	N/A	[97]

Table 8. Cont.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
cotton	persimmon tannin (PT), padding, laser dotting (L)	WCA (PT) = 145°, WCA (PT, laser power 2.4 w) = 138°, WCA (PT, laser power 4 W) = 110°, 5 different sites per sample	breaking strength (PT, warp) = +13% (PT-L, warp) = +1%, breaking strength (PT, weft) = +9%, (PT-L, weft) = −0.5% stiffness (PT, warp) = +53%, (PT-L, warp) = +49%, (PT, weft) = +47% (PT-L, weft) = +32%, WVTP (PT) = −7%, (PT-L) = −5% AP (PT) = −12% (PT-L) = −9% ANTI. P. (<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E.coli</i>) = 99,9%, UV protection UPF, UPF (PT) = +83% (41.35+ / −1.99) UPF(PT-L) = +82% (40.27+ / −0.67)	WD (AATCC 61–2010 [131], T, 250 domestic washing cycles)—WCA = 97°, AR (15000 cycles)—WCA = 134°	[51]

5.4. Biowaste

Common nanopolymeric fillers for superhydrophobic coatings can be synthesized from biowaste. Rice husks are a good example of agricultural waste that contains over 60% silica, 10–40% carbon, and other minerals which can be synthesized as byproducts during the process of rice husk gasification/pyrolysis [16]. A summary of studies using biowaste can be found in Table 9.

Seth and Jana et al. [132] chemically modified biowaste eggshell (ES) powder (deposited by drop cast) by food-grade natural beeswax (deposited by dipping). The results confirmed superhydrophobic character with WCA 156° and SA < 10°. The fabricated cotton had significant abrasion resistance. It can exhibit the potential to prevent biofilm formation and bacterial adhesion. The coated surface exhibits excellent antifouling properties toward commonly used food liquids (CA < 150°) and also prevents adherence to the liquids. In addition, the coating inhibits protein adsorption on its surface.

Costa et al. [133] pioneered the development of innovative formulations utilizing long-chain cellulose esters (LCCEs), derived from recycled cellulose sourced from textile residues, aligning with a circular approach aimed at functionalizing textiles. Hydrophobic cellulose derivatives were synthesized through esterification of the extracted cellulose with various carboxylic acids. Carboxylic acids of different chain lengths, including hexanoic acid, decanoic acid, tetradecanoic acid, hexadecanoic acid, and octadecanoic acid, were utilized. All treated textiles exhibited WCA greater than 125°. Specifically, the fabric treated with hexadecanoic acid achieved an impressive superhydrophobic WCA of 150°, demonstrating a “petal effect” where water drops exhibited high adhesion to the substrate, refusing to roll off. The coating withstands domestic machine washing. The thermal pre-treatment significantly enhanced the hydrophobicity of the samples. The thermal stability of cellulose modified with fatty acids decreased which was linked to a reduction in crystallinity resulting from the esterification reaction. The treatment had no discernible impact on the breathability of the fabrics.

Chen et al. [134] employed a chemical mechanical process to extract cellulose nanofibrils (CNFs) from peanut shell powder. These CNFs were further modified by incorporating methyltrimethoxysilane (MTMS) via a sol-gel method. Subsequently, a composite material consisting of nano-cellulose aerogel and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was applied to cotton fabric using a spray coating technique. The WCA reached 160° when both the aerogel and PDMS were applied to the fabric simultaneously. This enhancement was attributed to the creation of a textured surface composed of aerogel sheet-like particles combined with low surface energy substances, resulting in an effective superhydrophobic effect. The peanut shell cellulose nanofibrils aerogel possessed a three-dimensional sheet-like structure, formed through the aggregation of adjacent rod-shaped cellulose nanofibrils via hydrogen bonding during the drying process. The treated fabric exhibited excellent antifouling and self-cleaning properties. Moreover, the material demonstrated an oil–water separation efficiency. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis revealed that the peanut shell cellulose nanofibrils aerogel possessed a three-dimensional sheet-like structure, formed through the aggregation of adjacent rod-shaped cellulose nanofibrils via hydrogen bonding during the drying process.

Table 9. A summary of studies that fabricated hydrophobic textile coating from biowaste, N/A indicates that the data is not available.

Textile Substrate	Substances Used for the Coating and Process Techniques	Water Repellency (WCA, SA, Water Uptake, Water–Oil Separation) and Reproducibility	Change in Mechanical Properties (MP), WVTP, Air Permeability (AP), and Additional Properties: UV Protection (UV) and Antibacterial Properties (ANT. P.)	Durability (Washing (WD), Chemical (CD), Thermal (TD), and Abrasion Resistance (AR))	Ref.
100% cotton	eggshell (ES) powder, food-grade natural beeswax, bovine serum albumin (BSA), hexane, ethanol, drop casting, dip method	WCA (ES, beeswax) = 154°	N/A	AR (scotch tape and finger tests)—WCA = 154°	[132]
100% cotton	long-chain cellulose esters (LCCEs) from recycled textile waste, carboxylic acids, hexanoic acid, decanoic acid, tetradecanoic acid, hexadecanoic acid or octadecanoic acid, impregnated by exhaustion	WCA (hexadecanoic acid) = 150°, 8–10 different sites per sample	WVTP (hexadecanoic acid) = +0.8%	WD (ISO 6330: 2012 [135])—Textiles: Domestic washing and drying procedures for textile testing, T = 40° + ironing, 5 cycles)—150° TD (hexadecanoic acid) = −14–25% (250–306 °C)	[133]
100% cotton	CNCs (from peanut shell powder), MTMS, PMDS, sol-gel, spraying	WCA = 160°, oil–water separation efficiency = 82%	self-cleaning (methylene blue powder and solution), antifouling properties	N/A	[134]

Widely used naturally occurring compounds for the hydrophobization of cellulosic textiles are also ZnO and TiO₂. They can be found in nature as minerals. However, they are usually produced synthetically. As a hydrophobic modification, they are most often used in the form of nanoparticles that can be toxic as they can damage bacterial cell membranes under simulated solar irradiation [136]. In 2014 the European Commission declared that the use of zinc oxide nanoparticles in spray products cannot be considered safe as it can be toxic if inhaled and also added that even non-toxic particles can have a similar effect if inhaled [137]. In 2020 TiO₂ was classified as a carcinogen if inhaled [138]. That is why these compounds will not be described as a separate class of compounds in this review.

Figure 18 presents a comparison of hydrophobic efficiency (as measured by WCA), durability, changes in mechanical properties, and air permeability across various groups of

natural compound coatings and PFAS-based coatings. This comparative analysis, derived from the reviewed articles, forms the foundation for our conclusions.

Figure 18. (Left) Initial WCAs and WCAs after washing, chemical and abrasion durability. (Right) Change in the mechanical properties and air permeability when compared untreated material with treated one.

6. Conclusions and Future Perspectives

In conclusion, this review delved into environmentally conscious alterations of natural textiles, prompted by recent research highlighting the detrimental environmental and health effects of PFAS, prevalent in textile hydrophobization. Our objective was to assess the potential of natural-based hydrophobic coatings, exploring their ability to rival PFAS in terms of efficiency and longevity. The study by Forsman et al. [12] compared the performance of commercial synthetic sprays and waxes with their natural carnauba wax-based coating described in this review. Unlike commercial waxes, which compromise breathability with thicker layers, wax particle coatings deliver effective water-repellence while maintaining fabric breathability, thanks to their thin, open structure and enhanced surface roughness, resulting in a higher WCA.

Our evaluation, based on research data, was challenging due to the lack of standardized evaluation methods, particularly for durability. The methodologies varied widely, with significant differences in the number of cycles applied across studies. Despite these, we can conclude that natural-based alternatives can yield comparable hydrophobicity and durability to PFAS coatings as seen in Figure 18. When comparing natural based coatings natural polymers typically yielded the lowest WCA. However, some studies achieved exceptionally high WCAs with natural polymers, depending on the other compounds used for modification. As expected, our evaluation results also revealed that a significant challenge in this field is developing methods that provide effective and durable hydrophobic properties to natural textiles without compromising breathability, comfort, or biodegradability. Preserving air permeability is a major hurdle, particularly when multiple coating layers are applied, leading to elevated WCA but reduced air permeability. This trade-off can compromise comfort, especially in hot and humid conditions, inducing increased perspiration and discomfort for the wearer. On the other site the study using natural polymers zein and rosin managed to even improve breathability [99]. Hydrophobic coatings can also affect the mechanical properties of the textile, potentially resulting in increased stiffness and influencing drape, texture, and flexibility. Additionally, the coating can reduce tensile

strength and elongation at the textile's breaking point, ultimately diminishing its durability and lifespan.

As observed from Figure 18, the altered properties of pristine materials present challenges not only for natural-based coatings but also for PFAS solutions. Coating durability is contingent on the chemical bonds formed within the coating. Robust chemical bonds, achievable through grafting and crosslinking, enhance resistance to washing and abrasion. However, compounds that are not crosslinked often lack durability. Some studies indicate that, even if durable to some extent, the durability of these coatings can be relatively short-lived compared to the textile's lifespan, potentially reducing the usable lifespan of the clothing item. Figure 18 illustrates that washing durability is often a greater challenge for hydrophobic textile coatings than abrasion resistance, as the WCA tends to decline more substantially following washing tests. However, additional data and more comprehensive comparative results are required to draw definitive conclusions.

In the majority of cases, coatings composed exclusively of 100% natural compounds were not employed showing the importance of further research. Silicates, acrylates, and carbons are frequently utilized, often accompanied by the use of potentially toxic nanoparticles like zinc- and titanium-oxides and silica, highlighting the necessity for future research to identify safer alternatives. Authors have successfully substituted these nanoparticles with modified cellulose or wax nanoparticles. It is imperative to strive toward entirely natural-based and renewable solutions. The information gathered in this review emphasizes that the addition of synthetic compounds often enhances efficiency. However, there are instances where coatings comprising solely 100% natural materials achieved superhydrophobic WCAs. Pioneering studies, such as those by Forsman et al. [12] and Tian et al. [51], demonstrate promising outcomes. Although natural-synthetic PFAS-free coatings are generally more environmentally friendly than PFAS coatings, they can still have negative environmental and health impacts. The inclusion of synthetic compounds often compromises the biodegradability of the coating. Additionally, there is a dearth of literature data regarding the biodegradability of these coatings, a crucial indicator of environmentally sustainable solutions, as well as their cytotoxicity. Only one of the articles we evaluated assessed cytotoxicity [133]. Therefore, evaluating the life cycle assessment is crucial in the future to gain a true understanding of the sustainability of coatings.

Natural-based coatings show promise for industrial applications because of their sustainability and environmental benefits. However, their economic feasibility depends on several factors, such as higher raw material costs, specialized production processes, and achieving performance comparable to synthetic coatings. While initial production may be more expensive, advancements in material science and growing market demand for eco-friendly products could make these coatings more competitive. Additionally, stricter regulations and the potential for long-term cost savings through reduced environmental impact may drive adoption. Ultimately, their success depends on improving scalability, performance, and cost efficiency. Future research on natural-based coatings for hydrophobic textiles should focus on improving durability, scalability, and performance under diverse conditions. Investigating hybrid coating systems, expanding the range of natural materials, and optimizing production processes are key areas to explore. Additionally, studying the environmental impact, safety, and potential for self-healing or self-cleaning coatings could enhance their practicality and market appeal. Finally, tailoring these coatings for specific applications and conducting economic feasibility studies will be crucial for their commercial success. With a discerning selection of natural compounds and employment of appropriate chemical, physical, and deposition techniques, the replacement of PFAS and other synthetic compounds in textile coatings is an achievable aspiration.

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